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PROMETEO

A **PRO**abilistic fra**ME**work for coas**T**al and harbor
d**E**fense in the c**O**ntext of climate change

D2.1

Report on the proposed probabilistic design
framework and description of the application to
case studies

**WP2 - Development & Validation - Probabilistic assessment of the
performances of coastal and harbor defense
solutions**

M2.1 - Set-up of the probabilistic framework

M2.2 - Application of the probabilistic framework

O2

Task 2.1 – Task2.2 – Task 2.3

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List of symbols

Symbol	U.m.	Description
A	[m]	Length of the offshore extension of the caisson foundation base
a	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the EurOtop (2018) formula
B	[m]	Width of the caisson foundation base
b	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the EurOtop (2018) formula
b_{d_s}	[hour/m]	Empirical coefficient of the site-specific relationship H_{s0} - d_s
b_{ss}	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the site-specific relationship H_{s0} - h_{ss}
b_{T_m}	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the site-specific relationship H_{s0} - T_m
b_{T_p}	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the site-specific relationship H_{s0} - T_p
C_f	-	Cost of failure
C_g	[m/s]	Wave group velocity
C_{g0}	[m/s]	Wave group velocity in deep water
CB	-	Confidence bounds
c	[m]	Thickness of the caisson foundation base
D_{n50}	[m]	Mean nominal diameter of the armor units
Dir	[°N]	Wave origin direction
d	[m]	Water depth over the crest of the caisson rubble-mound basement
d_r	[-]	Discount rate
d_s	[hours]	Sea storm duration
EAC	-	Expected annual cost
EAC_{rep}	[€/unit length]	Expected annual cost of repair interventions
EAC_{eco}	[€/day]	Expected annual cost due to blockade economic activities
F_H	[N/m]	Horizontal wave force
F_u	[N/m]	Uplift wave force
f	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the van der Meer formulas
g	[m/s ²]	Acceleration gravity
H_{max}	[m]	Maximum wave height
H_s	[m]	Significant wave height at the toe of the structure
H_{s0}	[m]	Offshore significant wave height
$H_{1/250}$	[m]	Average of the highest 1/250 waves, corresponding to H_{max}
h	[m]	Water depth at the toe of the defense solution
h'	[m]	Distance between the caisson base and mean sea level
h_{at}	[m]	Astronomical tide
h_b	[m]	Water depth at a distance $5H_s$ offshore from the breakwater toe
h_c^*	[m]	Maximum height of the horizontal pressure wave diagram
h_m	[m]	Mean water depth at the toe of the defense solution
h_r	[m]	Leeward caisson freeboard
h_{ss}	[m]	Storm surge level
h_{wall}	[m]	Height of the wave wall measured with respect to the toe of the structure
k	[-]	Parameter for the calculation of the lower and upper limits of a Normal distribution
K_s	[-]	Shoaling coefficient

List of symbols

L	[years]	System lifetime
L_w	[m]	Wave length
L_{w0}	[m]	Wave length in deep water
l	-	Lower truncation limit of a Normal distribution
l_c	[m]	Wave wall width
M	[m]	Length of the leeward extension of the caisson foundation base
M_u	[N*m/m]	Moment of the uplift wave force
M_H	[N*m/m]	Moment of the horizontal wave force
M_{arch}	[N*m/m]	Moment of the Archimede's buoyant force
m	-	Mean of a generic normally distributed variable
N_f	[-]	Number of life cycles with at least one failure
N_{od}	[-]	Damage parameter
N_r	[-]	Number of independent life cycles of the system (i.e. realizations of the Monte Carlo simulation)
N_w	[-]	Number of incident waves
n_{SS}	[-]	Number of generated random sea states for one life cycle
P_f	[-]	Failure probability
$P_{f,L}$	[-]	Failure probability at the end of the lifetime
$P_{f,Lmax}$	[-]	Maximum acceptable failure probability at the end of the lifetime
$P_{f,t}$	[-]	Failure probability during t years
p_1	[N/m ²]	Horizontal wave pressure at mean sea level
p_3	[N/m ²]	Horizontal wave pressure at the toe of the caisson
p_4	[N/m ²]	Horizontal wave pressure at the top of seawall
p_u	[N/m ²]	Maximum uplift wave pressure
q_{lim}	[m ³ /s m]	Maximum acceptable mean wave overtopping discharge
R	[-]	Resistance of the system
R_c	[m]	Structure freeboard
r	[-]	Failure index
S	[-]	External solicitation
S_{arch}	[N/m]	Archimede's Buoyant force
s	[year ⁻¹]	Rate of growth of the failure probability during L years
T	[years]	Length of a generic time period
T_m	[s]	Mean wave period
T_{max}	[s]	Maximum wave period
T_p	[s]	Peak wave period
T_r	[years]	Return period
$T_{1/3}$	[s]	Wave period associated to H_s
t	[years]	Time
u	-	Upper truncation limit of a Normal distribution
$V_{immersed}$	[m ³]	Immersed volume according to Archimedes' principle
W	[N/m]	Self-weight of the caisson
X_{arch}	[m]	Arm of Archimede's buoyant force
X_g	[m]	Arm of self-weight of the caisson force
X_u	[m]	Arm of uplift wave force
Y_H	[m]	Arm of horizontal wave force
Z_{ULS}	[-]	Reliability function associated to an ultimate limit state
$Z_{ULS,o}$	[-]	Reliability function associated to the ultimate limit state for caisson overturning

$Z_{ULS,s}$	[-]	Reliability function associated to the ultimate limit state for caisson sliding
Z_{SLS}	[-]	Reliability function associated to a serviceability limit state
α	[m]	Scale parameter of the Weibull distribution of the significant wave height
$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$	[-]	Coefficients of the wave pressure diagram by Goda (2000)
β	[°]	Angle of wave attack
$\beta_0, \beta_1,$ β_{max}	[-]	Goda coefficients for the calculation of H_s
$\beta_0^*, \beta_1^*,$ β_{max}^*	[-]	Goda coefficient for the calculation of H_{max}
γ_β	[-]	Influence factor on wave overtopping for oblique wave attack (EurOtop, 2018)
Δ	[-]	Relative buoyant density of the armor units
Δr	[%]	Percentage relative difference between future and present r
Δs	[%]	Percentage relative difference between future and present s
γ_f	[-]	Friction coefficient of the EurOtop (2018) formula
λ	[event/year]	Average annual frequency of extreme wave events
κ	[-]	Shape parameter of the Weibull distribution of the significant wave height
σ	-	Standard deviation of a generic normally distributed variable
σ_h	[m]	Standard deviation of the water depth at the toe of the defense solution
$\sigma_{P_{f,t}}$	[-]	Standard deviation of the failure probability at the end of the lifetime
φ	[-]	Structure–soil friction coefficient
ζ	[m]	Location parameter of the Weibull distribution of the significant wave height
η^*	[m]	Elevation to which the wave pressure exerts during crest phase
θ	[-]	Sea bottom slope

1. Introduction

1.1 Statement of the problem

Coastal zones host many natural ecosystems and economic and social activities, which require protection from the action of the sea. The design of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a complex task, due to the difficulty to describe their response to wave loads as well as to include the stochastic nature of climate forcing. Nowadays, the existence of a huge number of aging defense structures and climate change-induced forcing variability highlight the need for sustainable maintenance and adaptation plans.

Uncertainties related to the non-conventional nature of historical or adapted structures and to the effects of climate change on marine climate must be properly considered during the design process. Traditional deterministic design methodologies do not take into account such uncertainties, whereas probabilistic design methods employ probability distribution functions of the involved variables to estimate the failure probability of a certain system. In the world, only a few national design guidelines started to use probabilistic approaches, which however refer just to newly built structures, while the effects of climate change are considered only in a simplified manner. In Italy, technical recommendations for maritime dikes and coastal defense solutions date back to the '90s and are still based on a deterministic approach. Moreover, though climate-aware engineering design is required, for example by EU guidelines for public work funding, no solid know-how is available to designers and decision-makers.

In this context, PROMETEO aims to foster a more resilient approach for the management of coastal areas, by developing a probabilistic design framework able to consider the uncertainties related to the response of new, existing or adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions and met-ocean forcing in a changing climate. To this scope, the critical review of existing design regulations, the collection of state-of-art design formulas, and the study of possible adaptation solutions of aging structures are carried out, with reference to four types of coastal and harbor defense solutions, namely rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments.

In the present report, the probabilistic calculation procedure for the assessment of the performances of defense interventions, defined on the basis of the information derived from the critical review of existing design regulations of WP1, is described. Moreover, the results of the application of this procedure to three Italian case studies, corresponding to target T2.1 and made possible by the research activities carried out within WP3 and WP4, are discussed.

1.2 Phases of the work

The present document is organized in the following two parts:

1. Chapter 2 contains the description of the developed probabilistic framework for the assessment of the performances of coastal and harbor defense solutions, which is based on the Monte Carlo simulation technique. Moreover, a set of performance and economic indexes for a clear and easy-to-interpret presentation of the results are proposed;

2. Chapter 3 contains the description of the application of the probabilistic design framework to three Italian case studies, namely the Catania harbor rubble-mound breakwater, the Vado Ligure harbor vertical breakwater and the Arenella harbor rubble-mound breakwater, as well as the discussion of the obtained results.

Finally, Chapter 4 provides a summary of the proposed probabilistic framework and of the performed analyses and draws the conclusion of the presented work, also highlighting possible future developments.

2. Set-up of the probabilistic design framework

2.1 Overview

The present section provides the description of the probabilistic design framework developed for the assessment of the performances of coastal and harbor defense solutions. First, the procedure for the calculation of the failure probability of a system is explained, focusing on the definition of reliability functions and on the implementation of a Monte Carlo simulation. Then, a methodology for the characterization of marine climate and the generation of random sea states is proposed. Finally, performance and economical indexes for the a clear and easy-to-interpret presentation of the results are proposed.

2.2 Assessment of the failure probability

2.2.1 Calculation of the failure probability

Coastal and harbor defense solutions can be vulnerable to multiple failure modes, which may or may not be interrelated depending on their structural characteristics. For instance, harbor breakwaters are susceptible to crown wall failure, toe scour, geotechnical instability, and excessive overtopping. Each failure mode is described by a limit state equation, usually derived from state-of-the-art design formulas or site-specific empirical relationships. The interrelationships between a system's potential failure modes are typically represented using a fault tree, which employs series and/or parallel logic structures (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002). The failure modes contained in a generic fault tree can be correlated through common parameters contained in the correspondent limit state equations (e.g. significant wave height, mean wave period, mean sea level), but also by physical interactions. Due to the complexity of the quantification of physical mutual interactions between failure modes, they are often neglected in the probabilistic calculations.

Following the methodology presented by Stagnitti et al. (2022) and inspired by Puertos del Estado (2010) for the calculation of the failure probability of harbor breakwaters, only independent failure modes are considered in the present work. The evaluation of the probability of failure of the defense solution referred to a single failure mode is performed with reference to its limit state equation, usually referred to as reliability function, expressed in one of the following forms:

$$Z = R - S \quad (2.1)$$

$$Z = \frac{R}{S} \quad (2.2)$$

where R represents the resistance of the system to external solicitations S . Both R and S include stochastic variables that can be described by probability density functions (PDFs). In particular, R accounts for variables related to the structure's geometry and materials, whereas S refers to those describing hydrodynamic forcing and water density. The failure probability of the system (P_f) related to the considered failure mode corresponds to the probability that R is lower than S or rather that Z assumes values lower than zero in the case of equation (2.1) or lower than one zero in the case of equation (2.2).

As schematically illustrated in the block diagram of Figure 2.1, the failure probability is computed using a Level III reliability approach based on the MC simulation technique. The process begins by selecting a representative cross-section of the defense solution, a specific failure mode, and a climate scenario (e.g., present or future conditions). For each configuration, N_r independent life cycles of the defense solution are randomly simulated. The duration of each life cycle corresponds to the design lifetime of the defense solution (L), which is determined according to its intended purpose and importance, following relevant design codes and guidelines.

Figure 2.1 Block diagram of the probabilistic methodology for the assessment of the performances of harbor breakwaters. N_r is the number of realizations of each MC simulation (selected through a preliminary analysis of the stabilization process of the failure probability during lifetime and of its coefficient of variation), L is the duration of the structure lifetime, n_{ss} is the number of sea storm occurring during the structure lifetime, and λ is the mean annual occurrence frequency of sea storms obtained from the extreme value analysis of wave climate.

Within each life cycle (i.e., one realization of the MC simulation), n_{ss} sea states are randomly generated, which can lead or not to the structure failure. This number is defined as the product of the lifetime L and the average annual frequency of extreme wave events (λ), obtained through directional extreme value analysis of the significant wave height, as detailed in Section 2.2.2. For each generated sea state, random values are drawn for key climate descriptors, i.e. mean sea level, significant wave height, wave period, sea storm duration, and storm surge, while accounting for the interdependencies among these variables using site-specific empirical relationships (see Section 2.2.2 for details).

In addition to climate variability, each life cycle includes a random sampling of structural geometry and material properties, as well as empirical parameters contained in Z . These variables are modeled as normally distributed, with geometry and material PDFs truncated to prevent physically unrealistic values. Conversely, physical constants (e.g., gravitational acceleration) and performance criteria (e.g., acceptable damage thresholds or maximum wave overtopping limits) included in Z are treated as deterministic.

Once all the N_r realizations of the MC simulation are generated, it is possible to evaluate Z corresponding to each sea state of each life cycle and then count the number of life cycles with at least one negative value of Z . Therefore, the failure probability of the structure during t -years ($P_{f,t}$) and its standard deviation are calculated as follows:

$$P_{f,t} = P_f(0, t) = \frac{N_f(0, t)}{N_r} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\sigma_{P_{f,t}} = \sigma_{P_f}(0, t) = \sqrt{\frac{P_f(0, t) \cdot [1 - P_f(0, t)]}{N_r}} \quad (2.4)$$

where $N_f(0, t)$ is the number of t -years periods with at least one failure. The optimal value of N_r , which enables the compromise between accuracy of the results and acceptable computational times, is selected through a preliminary analysis of the stabilization process of $P_{f,t}$ and of its coefficient of variation CV for increasing N_r . If the design lifetime of length L years is considered, the failure probability of the structure during its lifetime ($P_{f,L}$) and the corresponding standard deviation are computed ($\sigma_{P_{f,L}}$). It is worth to point out that $P_{f,L}$ can be calculated using both equation (2.3) or the following one:

$$P_{f,L} = \sum_{i=1}^L P_f(i-1, L) \quad (2.5)$$

2.2.2 Characterization of marine climate and generation of random sea states

As explained in Section 2.2.1, for each life cycle of the defense solution, n_{SS} sea states are randomly generated. Following the methodology proposed by Stagnitti et al. (2022), each sea state is characterized by the following parameters: mean sea level, significant wave height, mean wave direction, peak and mean wave period, sea storm duration, and storm surge level. The mean sea level and the significant wave height are described by their PDFs, while the remaining wave climate descriptors are correlated with the significant wave height through empirical relationships.

The mean sea level is expressed in terms of water depth at the toe of the defense solution (h). According to Castillo et al. (2006), it is assumed to follow a Normal distribution with standard deviation expressed as:

$$\sigma_h = \frac{(h_m + h_{at}) - (h_m - h_{at})}{4} \quad (2.6)$$

where h_m is the mean water depth at the toe of the defense solution and h_{at} is the astronomical tide at the studied site. If a future scenario is considered, the projected SLR is added to the present h_m .

Concerning the current wave climate, first the directional extreme value analysis of the offshore significant wave height (H_{S0}) is performed. The Peak Over Threshold (POT) method is applied to the historical time series of H_{S0} to identify extreme events, which are considered independent if they are separated by a minimum interval of 12 hours (Boccotti, 2004). The method of maximum likelihood estimation (MML) is then used to fit extreme value distributions to the data sample, and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test is employed to identify the best-fitting PDF.

The wave direction (Dir) is assumed to correspond to the bisector of the considered wave origin sector. The peak (T_p) and mean (T_m) wave period, sea storm duration (d_s) and storm surge height (h_{SS}) are expressed as functions of H_{S0} , using site-specific empirical relationships. In

particular, T_p and T_m are correlated with H_{s0} through the following equations, in the form proposed by Boccotti (2004):

$$T_p = b_{T_p} \pi \sqrt{\frac{H_{s0}}{4g}} \quad (2.7)$$

$$T_m = b_{T_m} \pi \sqrt{\frac{H_{s0}}{4g}} \quad (2.8)$$

where b_{T_p} and b_{T_m} are a site-specific non-dimensional coefficient determined by applying the least squares method to the dataset of H_{s0} - T_p and H_{s0} - T_m . The dependence of d_s on H_{s0} is described using the following relationship, inspired by the equivalent exponential storm model introduced by Laface and Arena (2016):

$$d_s = b_{d_s} H_{s0} \quad (2.9)$$

where b_{d_s} , expressed in hours/m, is a site-specific coefficient derived using the least squares method from the dataset of H_{s0} - d_s . Similarly, h_{SS} is related to H_{s0} by the following expression, is similar to the one proposed by Salmun et al. (2011):

$$h_{SS} = b_{SS} H_{s0} \quad (2.10)$$

where b_{SS} is another site-specific non-dimensional coefficient evaluated using the least squares method applied to the dataset of H_{s0} - h_{SS} .

The propagation of offshore sea states to the toe of the defense solution can be performed using different approaches depending on the site's characteristics. These may include analytical methods, numerical modeling, or a combination of both. For straight coastlines and uniform bathymetry, a simplified approach based on linear wave shoaling combined with breaking criteria can be employed. It is worth to point out that if the time series of the descriptors of propagated waves are already available, the probabilistic characterization of the wave climate parameters is directly performed at the toe of the defense solution.

Once the local marine climate is characterized, n_{SS} random sea states are generated for each simulated life cycle of the system. The process begins by drawing an initial random value of H_{s0} from the central fit of its corresponding PDF. As illustrated in Figure 2.2a, a final value of H_{s0} is then sampled from a Normal distribution with a mean equal to the initial value and a standard deviation based on the 95% confidence bounds of its PDF. For each wave climate variable that depends on H_{s0} , an initial value is computed using the central fit of the site-specific relationship (i.e. Equation (2.6), (2.7) or (2.9)), using the previously obtained final H_{s0} value. As shown in Figure 2.2b, a final value for each dependent variable is then drawn from a Normal distribution with a mean equal to its initial estimate and a standard deviation derived from the 95% confidence bounds of the corresponding site-specific formula. Finally, a random value of the water depth at the toe of the structure is sampled from a Normal distribution, with its standard deviation defined by Equation (2.6), and added to the previously generated h_{SS} . Wave propagation is then carried out.

Figure 2.2 Sketch of the procedure for the generation of (a) a random H_{s0} from the extreme value distribution of the significant wave height and (b) random H_{s0} -dependent variable from a site-specific empirical relationship.

2.3 Definition of performance and economic indexes

The following synthetic performance indexes are proposed to facilitate the interpretation of the MC simulation results:

- the failure index r , which quantifies the safety level ensured by the breakwater. It is defined as:

$$r = \frac{P_{f,L}}{P_{f,Lmax}} \quad (2.11)$$

where $P_{f,Lmax}$ is the maximum acceptable failure probability, determined based on the function and strategic importance of the system, in accordance with design standards and guidelines. If r is lower the one, the failure probability is unacceptable, otherwise the performances are sufficient;

- the rate of growth of the failure probability s , defined as the slope of the linear regression model that describes the variation in the failure probability over the system's life cycle, for t ranging from 0 to L years according to equation (2.2). The greater is s , the faster is the velocity at which the structure performances decrease. It is worth to point out that, in the absence of maintenance or upgrading interventions, s is always positive.

These indexes enable immediate comparison between different design solutions and/or climate scenarios, while also providing useful information for maintenance planning.

Following the procedure outlined in Figure 2.1, the failure probability and the previously defined synthetic indexes can be computed at different representative cross-section of the defense solution. The spacing between consecutive cross-sections should be chosen to adequately capture variations in marine climate, structural response, and design requirements. This

approach allows for the creation of spatial maps of r and s , offering a comprehensive overview of the system's performance and helping to identify potentially critical segments. Furthermore, the performance of a given design solution under present and future scenarios can be directly compared by computing the following percentage differences at each selected cross-section:

$$\Delta r = \frac{r_{fut} - r_{pres}}{r_{pres}} \cdot 100 \quad (2.12)$$

$$\Delta s = \frac{s_{fut} - s_{pres}}{s_{pres}} \cdot 100 \quad (2.13)$$

where the subscripts *pres* and *fut* refer to the present and future climate scenarios, respectively.

In addition to the above-described performance indexes, the return period (T_r) associated to a certain failure probability can be estimated according to the following equation (Consiglio Superiore dei Lavori Pubblici, 1996):

$$T_r = \frac{L}{-\ln(1 - P_{f,L})} \quad (2.14)$$

where L is the system lifetime. The return period provides information about the system performance in a format that is more readily usable by designers than the failure probability.

Finally, an index to quantify the risk of failure in economic terms is proposed, namely the cumulated Expected Annual Cost (EAC):

$$EAC(T) = \sum_{t=1}^T EAC(t) = \sum_{t=1}^T \left\{ [P_f(t) - P_f(t-1)] \times C_f \times \frac{1}{(1 + d_r)^t} \right\} \quad (2.15)$$

where $P_f(t)$ is cumulated failure probability at the year t , C_f is the cost of failure, which is supposed to be constant in time, D is the discount rate set equal to 0.03, and T is the length of the considered time period. If T is equal to L , the whole lifetime of the system is considered.

The evaluation of failure costs is not straightforward, due to the difficulty of obtaining documentation on the costs of repair interventions for different types of coastal and harbor defense structures, as well as the losses resulting from the system's lack of functionality. The repair cost can be estimated based on existing bills of quantities for repair interventions similar to the one of interest, updated according to the local official price list. Instead, losses resulting from lack of functionality can be assessed based on published financial statements of the economic activities that rely on the protection provided by the defense system, as well as based on economic estimates of damage to physical assets.

3. Application of the probabilistic design framework

3.1 Overview

The probabilistic framework for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions described in Chapter 2 is applied to three Italian case studies, reaching the target T2.1. The first case study is the Catania harbor breakwater, which is a rubble-mound structure with cubic armor units currently undergoing restoration and upgrading works aimed at enhancing its stability and reduce wave overtopping discharge. In particular, an upgraded version of the existing breakwater is considered for the assessment of the stability and overtopping performances under the present climate and two future scenarios of sea level rise, including the spatial variability of resistance and solicitation. The second case study is the harbor breakwater of Vado Ligure, which represents an emblematic example of upgrading solution for this kind of structure. In particular, the existing prefabricated monolithic cellular reinforced concrete caissons will be relocated offshore to enlarge the harbor basin. Also in this case, the stability and overtopping performances are assessed for two representative cross-sections, considering the present climate and two future scenarios. Finally, the third case study is the harbor breakwater of Arenella. This rubble-mound structure, composed of Accropode armor units, is planned to undergo extension works involving a typical cross-section geometrically similar to that of the existing structure. As for the other two case studies, the performance of the structure are assessed considering its stability and capability to reduce wave overtopping under the present climate and two future scenarios of sea level rise.

3.2 The case study of the Catania harbor breakwater

Description of the case study

The methodology for the probabilistic assessment of the spatial distribution of the structure performances is applied to the case study of the Catania harbor breakwater. As shown in Figure 3.1a, the Port of Catania is located in the central Mediterranean Sea, occupying a strategic position between the Suez Channel, the Strait of Gibraltar, European ports, and North-African ports.

As documented by Franco (1994), Oumeraci (1994) and Takahashi (2002), the outer breakwater of the Port of Catania was originally constructed in the XVIII century as a composite structure. It was later converted into a 2.25 km-long rubble-mound breakwater. Due to the significant deterioration of the armor layer, which consists of 62 t concrete cubes, the *Autorità di Sistema Portuale del Mare di Sicilia Orientale* is currently undertaking restoration and upgrading works to enhance the structural stability and reduce wave overtopping discharge.

The identification of the most effective upgrading solutions was based on the results of both experimental and numerical tests, partially presented by Stagnitti et al. (2020, 2023a,b). Among the evaluated options, the present study focuses on a solution that involves: (i) the addition of extra armor units identical to the existing ones, following the original 2:1 slope; (ii) the construction of a quarry stone toe berm; (iii) the raising of the wave wall up to +9.50 m above mean sea level.

Particular attention must be given to the design of the structure toe, which is known to be a critical component for the overall stability of a breakwater. In this specific case, the toe geometry is strongly influenced by the existing shape of the deteriorated armor layer. As schematically illustrated in Figure 3.1b, in cross-section type A, where the existing armor layer has undergone uniform degradation, the toe berm directly supports the additional cubic armor units. On the contrary, in cross-section type B, where the lower portion of the existing armor layer remains largely intact and retains the original 2:1 slope, the toe berm does not effectively support the added units, resulting in a condition that is intuitively less stable compared to type A.

To describe the geometric variations along the structure, 44 representative cross-sections were defined at about 50-meter intervals. Figure 3.2a presents a map of the Catania harbor breakwater, indicating the location and type of each cross-section (19 of type A and 25 of type B), while Figure 3.2b graphically displays the toe depth (h) of the structure at each defined cross-section, which ranges between 10 m and 20 m.

Figure 3.1 Case study of the Catania harbor breakwater: (a) location of the Port of Catania; (b) representative cross-sections of the upgraded harbor breakwater.

Figure 3.2 Characteristics of the Catania harbor breakwater: (a) spatial distribution of the cross-section types and indication of the representative wave data points for each stretch of the structure (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N); (b) plot of the toe depth (h) at each cross-section and indication of the acceptable mean wave overtopping discharge according to EurOtop (2018). The dashed lines indicate the separation between the four segments of the breakwater, each one corresponding to a wave data point.

The local wave climate was characterized using reanalysis data provided by the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service - CMEMS (Korres et al., 2021) and propagated towards the coast with the spectral wave propagation model SWAN (Booij et al., 1999), over a 30-year period from 1993 to 2022.

The CMEMS dataset was produced using the Med-WAV modeling system, based on the WAM 4.6.2 wave model. This model is forced by daily averaged currents from Escudier et al. (2020) and hourly ERA5 wind fields at a horizontal resolution of 0.25° (Hersbach et al., 2019). It operates over a primary computational domain with a spatial resolution of $1/6^\circ$, encompassing the Mediterranean Sea from 75°W to 10°E and from 70°N to 10°S . Additionally, a nested domain with higher spatial resolution ($1/24^\circ$) covers the region from 18.125°W to 36.2917°E and from 30.1875°N to 45.9792°N . At each grid point, hourly time series are available for key wave parameters, including significant wave height, mean wave direction, and both mean and peak wave periods.

The existing SWAN-based numerical model, developed within the framework of the Sicilian Regional Plan against Coastal Erosion (PRCEC,2020), was used to propagate offshore CMEMS data toward the shoreline. The model accounts for wave generation by wind, as well as energy dissipation due to breaking, whitecapping, and bottom friction. It also includes physical processes such as wave refraction, diffraction, shoaling, transmission, and reflection.

The computational domain, which encompasses all Sicilian coastal waters, was defined based on CMEMS grid points. Specifically, 53 offshore points, generally located at depths greater than 100 m, were selected to define the boundary conditions. Bathymetric data from the Italian Navy Hydrographic Institute and the GEBCO dataset, along with wind data from the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2019), were interpolated at each grid node.

The resolution of the unstructured computational grid was determined according to seabed depth. Given the large area of the domain, a cell size of 5000 m was used for depths greater or equal to 100 m, and 500 m for depths lower or equal to 50 m. For intermediate depths (50÷100 m), the cell size varies linearly between 500 m and 5000 m. In coastal areas with steep seabed slopes, cell size was further refined to approximately 250 m.

To capture the spatial variability of the wave climate along the Catania harbor breakwater, time series of significant wave height, mean wave direction, and mean wave period were extracted at the four data points shown in Figure 3.2a. The WGS84 coordinates and water depth of each data point are listed in Table 3.1. Additionally, Figure 3.2 illustrates the division of the breakwater into four segments, each corresponding to one of the wave data points.

In addition to the wave characteristics, the contribution of storm surge to sea level is considered. In particular, storm surge is characterized based on the 10-minute resolution time series of storm surge level extracted at the grid point of WGS84 coordinates 37.5370°E - 15.1390°N of the ERA5 reanalysis dataset (Hersbach et al., 2019) for the period 1993-2022.

Finally, the mean SLR projections from the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2022) are incorporated into the probabilistic calculations to account for future sea level changes at the site of interest. In particular, under the worst-case scenario SSP5-8.5, the projected mean SLR is 0.42 m by 2070 and 0.78 m by 2100.

Table 3.1 Coordinates and depth of the wave data points showed in Figure 3.2a (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N).

Wave data point	East [km]	North [km]	Depth [m]
P1	509080.137	4150554.015	20.5
P2	509196.969	4150015.957	22.6
P3	509305.495	4149319.991	23.0
P4	509283.901	4148888.405	22.2

Simulated failure mechanisms and climate scenarios

Two independent failure modes are analyzed, i.e. the collapse of the outer armor layer, which lead to an ultimate limit state (ULS), and the excessive mean wave overtopping discharge, which corresponds to a serviceability limit state (SLS). The reliability functions describing the two failure mechanisms are derived from Stagnitti et al. (2022).

In particular, the reliability function employed for the ULS due to the collapse of the outer armor layer is obtained by rewriting the traditional damage formula proposed by van der Meer (1988a), whose empirical coefficient f has been calibrated based on and updated version of the experimental data on upgraded rubble-mound breakwaters presented by Stagnitti et al. (2023b), which has been described in the deliverable D4.1:

$$Z_{ULS} = f \cdot \left(6.7 \frac{N_{od}^{0.4}}{N_w^{0.3}} + 1 \right) \cdot \Delta D_{n50} - H_s \cdot \left(\frac{2\pi H_s}{gT_m^2} \right)^{0.1} \quad (3.1)$$

where the probability distribution functions of the wave characteristics are determined according to the methodology described in subsection 2.2.2, and the number of incident waves

N_w is expressed as the ratio between the duration of sea storms and the mean wave period. The empirical coefficient (f), the mean nominal diameter (D_{n50}) and the relative buoyant density (Δ) of the armor units are assumed to follow a normal distribution, as suggested by Burcharth (1992) and van der Meer (1988b). The mean (m) and the standard deviation (σ) of the normally distributed variables are reported in Table 3.II. As regards the empirical coefficient f , it assumes different values depending on the cross-section type (see Figure 3.1). Moreover, the normal distributions of D_{n50} and Δ are truncated to exclude unrealistic values. The lower (l) and upper (u) truncation limits are calculated as a function of the parameter k :

$$l = m - k\sigma \quad (3.2)$$

$$u = m + k\sigma \quad (3.3)$$

The damage parameter N_{od} is considered as a deterministic variable and it is set equal to 2.00, which corresponds to the collapse of the outer armor layer according to the indications of CIRIA et al. (2007).

As regards the SLS, the reliability function results from rewriting the formula suggested by EurOtop (2018) to predict the mean wave overtopping discharge, considering the empirical coefficients a and b calibrated based on numerical data on upgraded rubble-mound breakwaters presented by Stagnitti et al. (2022) which has been described in the deliverable D4.1:

$$Z_{SLS} = q_{lim} - \sqrt{gH_s^3} \cdot a \cdot \exp \left[- \left(b \cdot \frac{R_c}{H_s Y_f} \right)^{1.3} \right] \quad (3.4)$$

where $R_c = h_{wall} - (h + h_{SS})$. Also in this case, the probabilistic characterization of the wave parameters is performed according to the methodology described in subsection 2.2.2. The parameter h_{wall} , which is the height of the wave wall measured with respect to the toe of the structure, is normally distributed, and its distribution is truncated to exclude unrealistic values. As discussed in subsection 2.2.2, the water depth h at the toe of the breakwater follows a Normal distribution too. The same holds for the empirical coefficients a and b . The parameters of the above-mentioned normal distributions are reported in Table 3.II. The mean value of the water depth at the toe of the structure, which is different at each cross-section, is reported for the present climate as well as for the future SSP5–8.5 scenario for the years 2070 and 2100. The standard deviation of h is calculated according to Equation (2.6), considering that for the site of Catania h_{at} is equal to 0.14 m. The mean value of h_{wall} varies with the cross-section toe depth, and the corresponding standard deviation is set as suggested by Lara et al. (2019). The acceptance limit q_{lim} is considered as a deterministic variable and, as shown in Figure 3.2, it is set equal to 0.001 m³/s m for the cross-sections located between progressive distances of 0 m and 1200 m, and 0.005 m³/s m for the remaining ones. Such limits correspond to the acceptable mean overtopping discharge to ensure safety for small boats and for larger yachts, respectively (EurOtop, 2018).

Following Stagnitti et al. (2022) and according to Puertos del Estado (2010), the lifetime of the harbor breakwater is assumed equal to 50 years, and the maximum acceptable failure probability ($P_{f,Lmax}$) is set equal to 10⁻¹, for both the ULS and the SLS. For each of the three considered climate scenarios, a MC simulation with $N_r=2.25 \times 10^4$ realizations (i.e. life cycles of the structure) is performed, to evaluate the probability to reach the ULS or the SLS.

Table 3.II Values of the mean (m) and the standard deviation (σ) of the normally distributed variables, and of the parameter k employed to calculate the lower (l) and upper (u) limits of the truncated distributions (f = empirical coefficient of the ULS reliability function, a and b = coefficients of the SLS reliability function, h = mean water depth, D_{n50} = mean nominal diameter, Δ = relative density, h_{wall} = height of the wave wall measured with respect to the toe of the structure).

Variable	Description	m	σ	k	l	u
f [-]	van der Meer (1988a) formula - type A cross-section	1.77	0.30	-	-	-
	van der Meer (1988a) formula - type B cross-section	1.37	0.22	-	-	-
a [-]	EurOtop (2018) formula - upgraded breakwaters	0.06	0.05	-	-	-
b [-]	EurOtop (2018) formula - upgraded breakwaters	1.50	0.15	-	-	-
h [m]	Present climate	10.20÷19.30	0.07	-	-	-
	SSP5-8.5 future scenario 2070	10.62÷19.72	0.07	-	-	-
	SSP5-8.5 future scenario 2100	10.98÷20.08	0.07	-	-	-
D_{n50} [m]	62 t cubes	3.00	0.03	3.00	2.90	3.10
Δ	-	1.23	0.05	4.00	1.04	1.42
h_{wall} [m]	Dependent on the toe depth of the cross-section	19.7÷28.8	0.03	4.00	19.58÷28.68	19.82÷28.62

Results and discussion

Characterization of wave climate and generation of random sea storms

The extreme value analysis is performed for the significant wave height data corresponding to the points shown in Figure 3.2, whose coordinates are reported in Table 3.I. Following the methodology described in subsection 2.2.2, the POT method is applied using a threshold equal to 1.5 m for the identification of independent events according to the definition provided by Boccotti (2004). A filter of 2.0 m is also employed to remove the lower values of significant wave height, in order to improve the robustness of the estimation of the probability distribution tail. As shown by the wave roses in Figure 3.3, the extreme events originate from the 30°-wide angular sectors centered at 90°N and 120°N, regardless of the data point considered. Moreover, the percentage distribution of the events by significant wave height and direction of origin is quite similar among the four data points.

The obtained samples of extreme events are composed by 88, 71, 75 and 77 elements for the wave data points P1, P2, P3 and P4, respectively. The average number of extreme events per year calculated for each sample is reported in Table 3.III. The MLM is employed to estimate the scale, shape and location parameters of the Weibull distribution at each wave data point, which are reported in Table 3.III. The goodness of fit is assessed at the 5% significance level using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test.

Figure 3.3 Wave roses showing the percentage of events classified by significant wave height (H_{s0}) and direction of origin for data points (a) P1, (b) P2, (c) P3, and (d) P4 close to the Catania harbor breakwater.

Table 3.III Average number of extreme events per year (λ) and values of the scale (α), shape (κ), and location (ζ) parameters of the Weibull distribution adapted to the extreme values of the significant wave height H_{s0} at points P1, P2, P3, and P4 close to the Catania harbor breakwater.

Wave data point	λ [events/year]	α [m]	κ [-]	ζ [m]
P1	2.93	0.75	1.17	2.01
P2	2.37	0.83	1.15	2.00
P3	2.50	0.81	1.06	2.00
P4	2.57	0.80	1.05	2.01

In order to quantify the variability of the extreme wave climate among points P1, P2, P3, and P4, values of significant wave height calculated from the Weibull distribution for different return periods are compared for each data point. Figure 3.4 shows that to increasing return periods correspond greater discrepancies between the values of H_{s0} estimated for the four data points. Indeed, the difference between the maximum and the minimum values of H_{s0} is equal to 0.13 m, 0.43 m, 0.55 m and 0.60 m for return period equal to 5, 50, 100, and 300 years, respectively.

Therefore, the spatial variability of the extreme wave climate is not negligible for the case analyzed in the present study, and it must be included in the assessment of the performances of the harbor breakwater. In particular, the severity of extreme climate in terms of wave energy content, which is proportional to the square of the significant wave height, gradually increases from point P1 to point P4.

Since the rounded λ is equal to 3 events/year for the four wave data points, according to methodology described in subsection 2.2, and in particular in Figure 2.2a, 150 random values of H_{s0} are generated for each of the 2.25×10^4 MC realizations at each wave data point, resulting in a total of 3.38×10^6 sea storms. For instance, Figure 3.5a shows the random values of H_{s0} generated for the wave data point P1, together with the central fitted curve and the 95% confidence bounds of the corresponding Weibull distribution.

In order to evaluate the mean wave period (T_m), the sea storm duration (d_s), and the storm surge height (h_{SS}) corresponding to each randomly generated value of H_{s0} , the site-specific coefficients of the empirical relationships described by equations (2.7) - (2.10) are calibrated for the four wave data points, using the least square methods. Table 3.IV reports their estimate and 95% *CBs*. Following the procedure described in subsection 2.2, and in particular in Figure 3.5b, for each random value of H_{s0} the corresponding values of T_m , d_s , and h_{SS} are generated at each wave data point.

Sea storm generated at the four wave data points shown in Figure 3.2 are propagated toward the toe of the structure, considering the present mean sea level as well as the two future projections. The presence of bathymetric contours parallel to the breakwater, together with the relatively small difference between initial and final water depths (i.e. up to 10.3 m), justifies the adoption of a simplified approach. This approach is based on linear wave shoaling computed following Dean and Dalrymple (1991), combined with the wave breaking criteria proposed by Kamphuis (1991) and Goda (2009).

Figure 3.4 Comparison between extreme values of significant wave height obtained from the Weibull distribution adapted to the extreme wave events of data points P1, P2, P3, and P4.

Figure 3.5 Generation of random sea storms for the wave data point P1: (a) random values of extreme significant wave height (H_{s0}) and central fit and 95% confidence bounds (CBs) of the corresponding Weibull distribution; (b) random values of mean wave period (T_m) and central fit and 95% CBs of the corresponding site-specific relationship with H_{s0} ; (c) random values of sea storm duration (d_s) and central fit and 95% CBs of the corresponding site-specific relationship with H_{s0} ; (d) random values of storm surge height (h_{SS}) and central fit and 95% CBs of the corresponding site-specific relationship with H_{s0} .

Table 3.IV Estimate and 95% confidence bounds (CBs) of the site-specific coefficients of the relationships between the significant wave height (H_{s0}) and the mean wave period (T_m), the sea storm duration (d_s), and the storm surge height (h_{SS}) calibrated for the wave data points P1, P2, P3 and P4.

Wave data point	Coefficient	Estimate	Lower 95% CB	Upper 95% CB
P1	b_{T_m} [-]	10.85	10.60	11.10
	b_{d_s} [h/m]	15.80	14.17	17.44
	b_{SS} [-]	-0.002	-0.010	0.005
P2	b_{T_m} [-]	10.62	10.34	10.89
	b_{d_s} [h/m]	16.59	14.98	18.20
	b_{SS} [-]	-0.003	-0.011	0.005
P3	b_{T_m} [-]	10.61	10.34	10.88
	b_{d_s} [h/m]	16.67	15.14	18.21
	b_{SS} [-]	-0.004	-0.011	0.004
P4	b_{T_m} [-]	10.66	10.39	10.94
	b_{d_s} [h/m]	16.79	15.25	18.33
	b_{SS} [-]	-0.003	-0.011	0.005

Spatial assessment of the stability performances under the present climate

The failure probability associated with the collapse of the outer armor layer is calculated at each cross-section of the Catania harbor breakwater by applying the methodology described in subsection 2.2.1, using the reliability function defined in equation (3.1) and the previously generated random present marine climate. It is worth to point out that the obtained results consider the spatial variability not only of the external solicitation, but also of the structure response. This is possible thanks to the empirical coefficient f of the reliability function Z_{ULS} , which allow to include the cross-section structural typology (i.e. A or B, see Figure 3.1b). The coefficient of variation of the computed failure probability at the end of the structure lifetime, which is given by the ratio between $\sigma_{P_{f,L}}$ (see equation (2.4)) and $P_{f,L}$ (see equation (2.3)), ranges between 0.04 and 0.38.

The performance indexes r and s described in subsection 2.3 are computed considering the present climate at each cross-section of the harbor breakwater. Figure 3.6 illustrates the results as a map. The color bar on the left represents the index r , whereas the one on the right refers to the index s .

Figure 3.6 Map of the performance indexes r and s computed for the Catania harbor breakwater considering the ultimate limit state due to the collapse of the outer armor layer under the present climate (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N).

At each cross-section, the failure index r is of the order of 10^{-1} . This reveals that the outer armor layer is sufficiently stable along the whole breakwater. The analysis of the spatial distribution of r along each of the four segments into which the structure is divided (see Figure 3.2) highlights that, for the same offshore wave climate (i.e. the same wave data point), the cross-section type A is characterized by the lower values of r . This is graphically less evident in the first segment, i.e. the one subjected to the less severe wave action. In this case, r is about 0.020 for the two type B cross-sections (i.e. the third and fourth ones) and ranges between 0.002 and 0.007 for the other ones. Therefore, the above discussed results confirm that the cross-section type A, which as illustrated in Figure 3.1b is characterized by the presence of a toe berm which directly support the outer armor layer, is the best performing one.

The spatial distribution of the rate of growth of the failure probability s is coherent with the spatial distribution of r , with a minimum and a maximum value of $5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ years}^{-1}$ and $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ years}^{-1}$, respectively. This means that for the most stable cross-sections (i.e. the ones characterized by smaller values of r), the rate at which the failure probability grows during the structure lifetime is lower.

The combination of the results obtained from the analysis of the spatial variability of the failure index and of the rate of growth of the failure probability along the breakwater allows the identification of the most critical cross-sections in terms of stability of the outer armor layer, which, as discussed above, are those characterized by the highest r and s . This information is useful for planning maintenance interventions to ensure that the design stability requirements are met throughout the entire service life of the structure. Priority should be given to those portions of the breakwater with a higher probability of damage to the outer armor layer and a higher rate of growth of this probability during lifetime, although for the present case study it remains below the acceptance limit. Moreover, by knowing the growth rate of the failure probability and setting a limit value $P_{f,L}$, the appropriate timing of repair interventions can be determined for each portion of the structure. Certainly, real-time field data from a monitoring system could integrate the outcomes of the probabilistic analyses, allowing the optimization of the maintenance strategy.

Spatial assessment of the overtopping performances under the present climate

Following the same approach used for the ultimate limit state due to the collapse of the outer armor layer, the failure probability associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge is computed at each cross-section of the Catania harbor breakwater by applying the methodology described in subsection 2.2.1, using the reliability function defined in equation (3.2) and the previously generated random present marine climate. Besides the spatial variability of wave action, the differences in the design requirements are included by considering a variable maximum acceptable mean wave overtopping discharge, following the indications reported in Figure 3.2. In this case, the coefficient of variation of the computed failure probability at the end of the structure lifetime falls in the range $0.01 \div 0.02$.

Figure 3.7 shows the spatial distribution of the computed performance indexes r and s , whose definition is presented in subsection 2.3. Also in this case, the color bar on the left represents the index r , whereas the one on the right refers to the index s .

The failure index r related to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge assumes values between 1.08 and 3.10, thus indicating that the breakwater is not able to ensure the design

requirements at any cross-section. The structure segment which exhibits the worst performances is the one corresponding to the wave data point P2 (see Figure 3.2). This result is attributable to the lower acceptable maximum mean wave overtopping discharge (i.e. $q_{lim} = 0.001 \text{ m}^3/\text{s m}$) adopted for the first two segments of the breakwater (i.e. the ones corresponding to wave data points P1 and P2, see Figure 3.2) as well as to the greater severity of the offshore wave climate at point P2 compared with point P1 (see Figure 3.4). The other three branches are characterized by similar values of r , with the minimum corresponding to the first cross-section of the first segment.

As in the case of the ULS related to the collapse of the outer armor layer, the spatial distribution of the rate of growth of the failure probability s is coherent with the spatial distribution of r . Therefore, the best performing cross-sections are also the ones with the lower rate of growth of the failure probability during lifetime. However, for the SLS caused by excessive mean wave overtopping discharge s is one order of magnitude smaller than in the case of the ULS, with values ranging between $2.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ years}^{-1}$ and $6.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ years}^{-1}$.

Figure 3.7 Map of the performance indexes r and s computed for the Catania harbor breakwater considering the serviceability limit state due to excessive mean wave overtopping under the present climate (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N).

The results of the probabilistic analyses highlight that upgrading interventions along the whole structure are needed to ensure acceptable failure probability due to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge, i.e. r lower than one. According to the indications of the map of the spatial distribution of r and s , priority should be given to the second segment of the breakwater, followed by the third and fourth segments, and finally the first segment. The identification of the best performing upgrading solution among different possible options could be achieved through the implementation of new probabilistic calculations and the comparison between the obtained performance indexes, similarly to the work presented by Stagnitti et al. (2022).

Effects of climate change on the structure performances

The SLR can affect the failure probability in two ways: i) by influencing the wave shoaling and propagation processes, and hence the wave characteristics at the toe of the breakwater; ii) by directly influencing the failure mechanism, being included into the corresponding reliability function. In order to quantify the effects of SLR on the structure performances, the failure probability associated with the collapse of the outer armor layer and with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge is calculated at each cross-section of the Catania harbor breakwater also considering the effects of projected SLR by 2070 and 2100. The coefficient of variation of the failure probability ranges between 0.04 and 0.32 for the ULS, while is about 0.01 for the SLS. Following the methodology described in subsection 2.3, the percentage difference between future and present values of r and s is computed (i.e. Δr and Δs , respectively), considering the SLR projections by 2070 and 2100.

Figure 3.8 shows the spatial distribution of Δr and Δs related to the ULS due to the collapse of the outer armor layer for the two future climate scenarios. The reliability function Z_{ULS} defined by equation (3.1) does not include the water depth. Therefore, SLR does not play a direct role on the outer armor layer stability, but only on wave propagation processes. Considering the future projection by 2070, Figure 3.8a reveals that SLR causes a modest increase of the failure index r , in the range 0÷13% for most of the cross-sections, with some values up to 38%. The highest Δr are observed at the lower water depths of each segment, where the influence of water level variations on wave propagation processes is higher. Figure 3.8b shows that the projected SLR by 2100 also induce modest Δr , which ranges between 6% and 16% for most of the cross-sections of the breakwater, with some values up to 52%. The highest values of Δr are obviously observed at the lower water depths of each segment. It should be noted that the projected future increase in the failure index r is limited in magnitude, ensuring that the structural stability remains within acceptable performance levels even under SLR conditions.

Figure 3.8 Map of the percentage difference between the performance indexes computed for the future climate with SLR and the present one, considering the ultimate limit state due to the collapse of the outer armor layer: (a) index r and future scenario SSP5-8.5 by 2070; (b) index r and future scenario SSP5-8.5 2100; (c) index s and future scenario SSP5-8.5 by 2070; (d) index s and future scenario SSP5-8.5 by 2100 (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N).

Figure 3.8c-d shows that the spatial distribution of Δs is similar to the spatial distribution of Δr , regardless of the considered future projection. This indicates that SLR affects the rate of growth of the failure probability inducing an increase comparable to the increase of r , further reducing the structure performances related to the stability of the outer armor layer.

The spatial distribution of Δr and Δs related to the SLS due to excessive mean wave overtopping for the two future climate scenarios is presented in Figure 3.9. Since the reliability function Z_{SLS} defined by equation (3.2) includes the water depth, SLR directly influences not only wave shoaling and breaking, but also wave overtopping processes. As demonstrated by Stagnitti et al. (2022), the reliability function expressed by equation (3.2) is more strongly affected by variations in significant wave height at the toe of the structure than by changes in mean sea level. Therefore, the direct influence of SLR on wave overtopping processes is dominant in deeper waters. On the contrary, in shallower waters, where wave characteristics are more strongly influenced by variations in mean sea level, the effect of SLR on wave propagation prevails, leading to overall more significant impacts on wave overtopping.

Figure 3.9a-b shows that Δr caused by SLR projected for the years 2070 and 2100 is positive at each cross-section, which means that, as expected, SLR causes the reduction of the structure performances in terms of protection from wave overtopping. In particular, as reported in Figure 3.9a, the percentage increase of the failure index r by 2070 is equal to about 40% for the first structure segment, 28% for the second one, and 32% for third and fourth ones. The only exception is represented by the cross-section at root (i.e. the one with the lower toe water depth), for which Δr is equal to 88%. Figure 3.9b shows that Δr induced by SLR by 2100 is approximately 85% for the first structure branch, 55% for the second one, and 65% for third and fourth ones. Also in this case the cross-section at root present an exceptional value of Δr , which is 175%. Therefore, as expected, the largest increase in r is observed at the shallowest water depths of the first segment, where the effects of SLR on wave characteristics are most pronounced. The second-largest values of Δr occur at the greatest water depths, i.e. at the third and fourth segments, where the direct influence of SLR on wave overtopping processes becomes more significant.

Figure 3.9 Map of the percentage difference between the performance indexes computed for the future climate with SLR and the present one, considering the serviceability limit state due to excessive mean wave overtopping: (a) index r and future scenario SSP5-8.5 by 2070; (b) index r and future scenario SSP5-8.5 2100; (c) index s and future scenario SSP5-8.5 by 2070; (d) index s and future scenario SSP5-8.5 by 2100 (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N).

Figure 3.9c-d shows that the spatial distribution of the percentage variation of the index s is similar to Δr for both considered future scenarios, as in the case of the ULS related to the collapse of the outer armor layer. Therefore, SLR induces an increase in the rate of growth of the failure probability that is comparable to that of r , also when considering the structure performances related to the protection against wave overtopping.

The combination of the outcomes obtained for the ULS and the SLS allow to confirm that the failure mode due to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge is the most critical. Indeed, besides the fact that the structure performances in protecting the harbor basin from wave overtopping are already not sufficient under the present climate, it emerges that this failure mechanism is characterized by the highest values of Δr and Δs , and hence it is more influenced by variations in mean sea level than the stability of the outer armor layer. Therefore, the results discussed provide useful insights for planning maintenance and upgrading interventions by prioritizing those failure mechanisms most likely to be negatively affected by SLR. Such results also offer guidance for identifying the most critical portions of the breakwater (i.e., those characterized by the highest r) and for establishing a maintenance schedule that accounts for the spatial variability in the growth rate of failure probability under SLR conditions.

Evaluation of the return period of failure during lifetime

The failure probability at the end of the structure lifetime, calculated at each representative cross-section, is converted into the corresponding return period using equation (2.14). Figure 3.10 shows the results obtained for the present climate and the two SLR future scenarios. The return period corresponding to the maximum acceptable failure probability during lifetime, which is equal to 475 years, is plotted as reference.

Figure 3.10a shows that the return period associated to the collapse of the outer armor layer is greater than 2000 years, and therefore far greater than the limit T_r , despite of the considered climate scenario. Such a result is obviously coherent with the findings derived from the analysis of the index r , which have already revealed the good stability performances of the breakwater. On the contrary, Figure 3.10b indicates that, under present climate conditions, the return period associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge along the breakwater ranges between 140 and 300 years. This finding demonstrates that the structure performance in terms of mean wave overtopping discharge does not satisfy the design requirements, as previously highlighted by the analysis of the failure index r . The projected sea-level rise (SLR) further exacerbates wave overtopping processes, resulting in a deterioration of structural performance. The corresponding return periods decrease to approximately 100÷170 years and 75÷135 years under the 2070 and 2100 scenarios, respectively.

Figure 3.10 Return period corresponding to the failure probability at the end of the structure lifetime at each representative cross-section of the Catania harbor breakwater, considering the present and future scenarios: (a) ULS associated to the collapse of the outer armor layer; (b) SLS associated to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge. The return period corresponding to the maximum acceptable failure probability during lifetime is plotted as reference.

Evaluation of the expected annual cost at the end of the lifetime

The cumulated Expected Annual Cost (*EAC*) is calculated at each representative cross-section of the breakwater using equation (2.15), distinguishing between ULS due to the collapse of the outer armor layer and SLS due to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge. With reference to the ULS, two categories of costs are considered:

- repair costs (expressed in € per unit length), estimated on the basis of the bill of quantities from the detailed upgrading design provided by the local Port Authority and updated according to the latest Official Regional Unit Price List (ORUPL);
- costs associated with the interruption of port operations (expressed in €/day), derived from the 2026 forecast budget published by the local Port Authority and integrated with the data reported in the Port System Master Plan of the Eastern Sicily Sea.

For the SLS, only costs associated with the interruption of port operations are considered. It should be noted that the *EAC* is calculated with reference to current climate conditions only. Indeed, the assessment of future climate scenarios would require projections of future costs, which fall beyond the scope of the present study. Moreover, both repair and economic costs are assumed to be uniform across all cross-sections. A more detailed cost assessment would require specialized studies, which cannot be undertaken within the scope of the present work.

In order to estimate the repair cost, the number of displaced units corresponding to the collapse of the outer armor layer (N_{moved}) is calculated from the definition of N_{od} :

$$N_{od} = \frac{N_{moved}}{B/D_{n50}} \quad (3.5)$$

where N_{od} is set equal to 2, as suggested by CIRIA et al. (2007), D_{n50} is equal to 3.0 m and B , which is the width of the considered breakwater segment, is set equal the distance between two

consecutive cross-sections, i.e. 50 m. Under these assumptions, N_{moved} is equal to 33. Table 3.V presents the estimate of the repair costs, considering three scenarios of collapse of the outer armor layer:

1. scenario 1: all displaced armor blocks are considered lost and must be replaced with new ones (worst-case scenario);
2. scenario 2: half of the displaced armor blocks are considered lost and must be replaced with new ones, while the remaining half is simply repositioned;
3. scenario 3: all displaced armor blocks are simply repositioned (best-case scenario).

Table 3.V reports the costs associated with the interruption of port operations. The 2026 forecast budget provides annual estimates referring to all ports managed by the local Port Authority. According to the Port System Master Plan of the Eastern Sicily Sea, 12.69% of the operational port area belong to the Port of Catania. Therefore, this percentage is applied to isolate the corresponding share of costs for the port of Catania. The conversion from €/year to €/day is performed under the assumption that revenues from port activities are uniformly distributed throughout the year.

Table 3.V Estimate of the repair cost for the Catania harbor breakwater in the case of collapse of the outer armor layer (ORUPL= Official Regional Unit Price List).

ORUPL ID	Brief description	Unit cost [€/m ³]	Quantity [m ³]			Total cost [€/50 m]		
			Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
17.2.1	Underwater recovery of natural rocks or artificial concrete blocks, including transport and placement.	48.17	0	459	891	-	22,110.03	42,919.47
17.3.1	Construction of artificial parallelepiped or prismatic concrete blocks (strength class C35/45, exposure class XS2, consistency class S3).	337.68	891	459	0	300,872.88	154,995.12	-
17.3.8	Random placement of parallelepiped or prismatic artificial concrete blocks.	45.45	891	459	0	40,495.95	20,861.55	-
Total cost [€/50 m]						341,368.83	197,966.70	42,919.47

Table 3.VI Estimate of the costs associated with the interruption of port operations for the Port of Catania.

Forecast budget ID	Activity Description	Forecast budget 2026 [€/year]	
		Ports of Eastern Sicily	Port of Catania
E121/10	Revenue from taxes on embarked and disembarked goods (Chapter III, Title II of Law No. 82/1963)	-	-
E121/15	Revenue from port charges (Art. 2 DPR 107 of 28/05/2009)	21,700,000.00	2,753,730.00
E121/30	Revenue from anchorage dues (Capo I, Tit.I, L.82/63 e s.m.)	8,850,000.00	1,123,065.00
E121/40	Revenue from authorizations for port operations (art.16 L. 84/94)	295,000.00	37,435.50
E122/20	Revenue from passenger traffic services	-	-
Total annual revenue [€/year]		30,845,000.00	3,914,230.50
Total daily revenue [€/day]		84,506.85	10,723.92

Figure 3.11 shows the expected annual repair cost during the structure lifetime (EAC_{rep}), calculated at each representative cross-section considering the collapse of the outer armor layer under the present climate. As expected, the cost scenario 1, which corresponds to the loss of all displaced armor blocks, presents the highest values of EAC_{rep} , ranging from 185 to 20,000 €/50 m (see Figure 3.11a). For cost scenarios 2 and 3, EAC_{rep} falls in the range $110 \div 11,500$ €/50 m and $25 \div 2,500$ €/50 m, respectively (see Figure 3.11b-c). Under the simplifying assumption of uniform repair costs along the breakwater, the spatial distribution of EAC_{rep} depends solely on the spatial distribution of the failure probability, i.e. of the failure index r .

The spatial distribution of the expected annual cost associated to the interruption of port operations (EAC_{eco}) resulting from the collapse of the outer armor layer is shown in Figure 3.12. The values of EAC_{eco} range between 5 and 650 €/day. Also in this case, the spatial distribution of expected annual cost mirrors the one of the failure index r , since the cost of port activity interruption is assumed to be uniform along the breakwater.

Finally, Figure 3.13 shows the spatial distribution of the expected annual cost at the end of the structure lifetime associated to the interruption of port operations (EAC_{eco}) resulting from excessive mean wave overtopping discharge. EAC_{eco} assumes values between 2,500 and 7,200 €/day. The higher EAC_{eco} associated with the SLS compared to that associated with the ULS is attributable to the higher failure probability at each representative cross-section for the former limit state. Under the assumption of uniform cost of port activity interruption along the structure, the spatial distribution of expected annual cost again corresponds to the one of the failure index r .

Figure 3.11 Map of the expected annual repair cost during the structure lifetime (EAC_{rep}) computed for the Catania harbor breakwater considering the ultimate limit state due to the collapse of the outer armor layer under the present climate (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N): (a) repair scenario 1 (all displaced armor blocks are considered lost and must be replaced with new ones); (b) repair scenario 2 (half of the displaced armor blocks are considered lost and must be replaced with new ones, while the remaining half is simply repositioned); (c) repair scenario 3 (all displaced armor blocks are simply repositioned).

Figure 3.12 Map of the expected annual cost of interruption of port activities during the structure lifetime (EAC_{ecc}) computed for the Catania harbor breakwater considering the ultimate limit state due to the collapse of the outer armor layer under the present climate (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N).

Figure 3.13 Map of the expected annual cost of interruption of port activities during the structure lifetime (EAC_{ecc}) computed for the Catania harbor breakwater considering the serviceability limit state due to excessive mean wave overtopping under the present climate (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N).

3.3 The case study of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater

Description of the case study

The methodology for the probabilistic assessment of structural and hydraulic performances of coastal and harbor defense structures is applied to the case study of the vertical breakwater of the Port of Vado Ligure (Italy). As illustrated in Figure 3.14, it is located in the Ligurian Sea, along the north-western coast of Italy, occupying a strategic position for the commercial traffic of Northern Italy as well as for maritime connections with the main ports of the western Mediterranean. In particular, the port plays a primary role in Europe as the leading hub for fruit imports and represents one of the major Italian ports for passenger and freight traffic to Corsica, Sardinia, and North Africa. Moreover, together with the other ports included in the Western Ligurian Sea Port Authority and owing to its proximity to the Gotthard Base Tunnel, the Port of Vado Ligure constitutes one of the main southern gateways to Europe for seaborne trade.

Figure 3.14 Case study of the Vado Ligure vertical breakwater: location and configuration of the port.

The proposed methodology is specifically implemented within the framework of the upgrading intervention concerning aimed at enlarging the harbor basin. The project, proposed by the *Autorità di Sistema Portuale del Mar Ligure Occidentale*, involves the relocation of the existing caissons further seaward and the construction of two additional caissons, with the objective of increasing the operational capacity and enhancing the overall structural performance of the breakwater.

In order to evaluate the variation of the performances of the harbor breakwater introduced by the new design configuration in terms of probability of failure, two characteristic cross-sections, namely C and D, are analyzed (see Figure 3.15). This choice stems from the need to ensure consistency in the application of the adopted formulations for vertical breakwaters, allowing for a direct and coherent comparison of the results obtained for both sections. In this way, any differences observed in the performances can be attributed exclusively to the differences between the caisson geometry and to the considered wave load conditions. The main geometric characteristics of cross-sections C and D are reported in Table 3.VII. It should be noted that cross-sections A and B shown in Figure 3.15a, which present characteristics typical of a composite breakwater, are not studied in the present work, since its focus is represented by vertical breakwaters. Concerning cross-section E shown in Figure 3.15a, it is not considered for the analysis because it is a head section, and hence it is subjected to three-dimensional loading conditions, which would require the use specific formulations for the assessment of the structure performances.

Figure 3.15 The Vado Ligure harbor breakwater: (a) layout of the existing and new configurations, with the indication of the representative cross-section types; (b) sketch of the representative cross-section C and D.

Table 3.VII Main geometric characteristics of the representative cross-sections C and D of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater.

Cross-section	h [m]	h' [m]	d [m]	R_c [m]	h_r [m]	B [m]	A [m]	M [m]	c [m]	θ [%]
C	46.00	25.50	24.00	7.00	2.50	23.50	1.50	1.50	0.80	3.18
D	46.50	19.50	18.00	7.00	2.50	20.50	1.50	1.50	0.95	3.64

For the current climate conditions, the local wave climate is characterized on the basis of reanalysis data provided by the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS; Korres et al., 2021), already cited in Section 3.2, over a 38-year period from 1985 to 2022. The offshore wave data point is located approximately 4.0 km from the coastline, at a water depth of about 150 m. The geographic coordinates of this point in the WGS84 system are 44.271° N and 8.5° E. In addition to the wave characteristics, the contribution of storm surge to sea level is considered. In particular, storm surge is characterized based on the hourly resolution time series of storm surge level extracted at the grid point of WGS84 coordinates 44.26°N – 8.474° E of the ERA5 reanalysis dataset (Hersbach et al., 2019) for the period 1985-2022. Offshore wave conditions are subsequently propagated toward the nearshore area by means of the simplified transformation method proposed by Goda (2000), which is described in detail in the following subsection. Two future scenarios are also considered, based on the projected sea level rise (SLR) estimates provided by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2022) for the site of interest. Our analysis focused on the SSP5-8.5 scenario, under which the mean sea level in the study area is expected to rise by 0.40 m by 2070. Looking further ahead to the end of the century (2100), the rise is projected to reach 0.75 m.

Propagation and design wave height

Wave propagation to the structure toe is carried out using the simplified method proposed by Goda (2000), which respect to the implementation of SWAN simulation allow reduce the computation times, while maintaining reliable results at the high depths typical of the case study. This method is employed for each offshore wave height (H_{s0}) generated through the MC simulation technique according the procedure described in section 2.2.2. The adopted wave propagation method accounts for shoaling and a wave height limitation due to breaking, while diffraction and refraction effects are neglected, as the computations are performed over relatively deep water. As waves propagate through a channel of gradually decreasing depth but constant width, both the wavelength and celerity decrease approximately as predicted by linear wave theory, while the wave height simultaneously changes. This variation in wave height, known as wave shoaling, is caused by the change in the energy propagation speed, i.e., the group velocity, with water depth. For small-amplitude waves with a single period, the change in wave height due to the shoaling effect can be calculated using standard predictive equations:

$$K_s = \frac{H_s}{H_{s0}} = \sqrt{\frac{C_{g0}}{C_g}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left[1 + \frac{4\pi h/L_w}{\sinh(4\pi h/L_w)}\right] \tanh \frac{2\pi h}{L_w}}} \quad (3.6)$$

Furthermore, for a specified water depth, the significant wave height can be readily estimated with minimal difficulty by:

$$H_s = \begin{cases} K_s H_{s0} & : h/L_{w0} \geq 0.2 \\ \min\{(\beta_0 H_{s0} + \beta_1 h), \beta_{max} H_{s0}, K_s H_{s0}\} & : h/L_{w0} < 0.2 \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

where the β coefficients are determined with the equations below, in which θ corresponds to the tangent of the seabed angle (in degrees):

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta_0 &= 0.028(H_{s0}/L_{w0})^{-0.38} \exp[20 \theta^{1.5}] \\
\beta_1 &= 0.52 \exp[4.2 \theta] \\
\beta_{max} &= \max \{0.92, 0.32(H_{s0}/L_{w0})^{-0.29} \exp[2.4 \theta]\}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

In the literature, it is not recommended to design vertical breakwaters using the significant wave height H_s at the structure toe, since it does not represent the most severe conditions for design purposes. Instead, the higher wave height H_{max} , more representative of extreme events for this type of structures, should be employed. To ensure methodological consistency with the Goda method for pressure distribution, the design wave height recommended by Goda (2000) is adopted, namely the maximum wave height computed as the average of the highest 1/250 waves ($H_{1/250}$). It is therefore possible to determine the design wave height H_{max} starting from H_s . Specifically, in the offshore region, this wave height is taken as $H_{max} = 1.8 H_s$, whereas within the surf zone, the wave height is represented by the highest random breaking wave, evaluated at a point located $5 H_s$ seaward of the breakwater:

$$H_{max} \equiv H_{1/250} = \begin{cases} 1.8 K_s H_{s0} & : h/L_{w0} \geq 0.2 \\ \min\{(\beta_0^* H_{s0} + \beta_1^* h), \beta_{max}^* H_{s0}, 1.8 K_s H_{s0}\} & : h/L_{w0} < 0.2 \end{cases} \tag{3.9}$$

where the β^* coefficients are determined with the equations below, in which θ corresponds to the tangent of the seabed angle (in degrees).

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta_0^* &= 0.052(H_{s0}/L_{w0})^{-0.38} \exp [20 \theta^{1.5}] \\
\beta_1^* &= 0.63 \exp [3.8 \theta] \\
\beta_{max}^* &= \max \{1.65, 0.53(H_{s0}/L_{w0})^{-0.29} \exp [2.4 \theta]\}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

It should be noted that H_{s0} is the offshore wave height, unaffected by propagation, diffraction, or refraction, h represents the water depth at the toe of the structure, and L_{w0} is the offshore wavelength. The period corresponding to this maximum wave is assumed to be equal to that of the significant wave, i.e., $T_{max} = T_{1/3} \cong T_p / 1.1$. This formulation provides all the variables necessary for estimating wave pressure diagram acting on the vertical breakwater.

Simulated failure mechanisms and climate scenarios

Three independent failure modes are analyzed: the sliding and overturning of the caisson, which lead to ultimate limit states (ULSs); the excessive mean wave overtopping discharge, which corresponds to a serviceability limit state (SLS).

In this analysis, sliding and overturning are considered independent failure modes. The reliability functions adopted to verify the ULSs due to sliding or overturning of the caisson are derived by applying the theory of Goda (2000) for the evaluation of the wave pressure diagrams as a function of the height H_{max} and the period T_{max} . It is worth to point out that the possible occurrence of impulsive waves is neglected, and only non-impulsive wave conditions are considered. This assumption is reasonable, considering that the caisson is located in deep waters and that the waves directional reach the structure with angles greater than 20° . The wave force contributes to destabilizing the caisson, together with the Archimedes' force (buoyant force), which depends on the considered sea level rise, storm surge and astronomic tide. The stabilizing forces generated by the self-weight of the caisson are different for each type of caisson (i.e. C

or D), because it depends on its geometry. In Figure 3.16, the destabilizing and stabilizing forces acting on the caisson are schematized, with their respective arms. The diagram also shows the *OB* point, which is considered the center of rotation in the overturning analysis.

Figure 3.16 Schematic representation of destabilizing and stabilizing forces and relative arms acting on the caisson for sliding and overturning checks.

The reliability function describing the sliding failure mode provides a measure of the caisson's structural safety against horizontal movement. It represents the balance between stabilizing forces R , which primarily arise from the self-weight of the caisson (W) combined with the uplift force (F_u) due to wave crests and the Archimedes' buoyant force (S_{arch}), multiplied by the structure–soil friction coefficient (φ), and destabilizing forces S , which are represented by the horizontal wave-induced loads acting on the structure during the wave crest phase (F_H):

$$Z_{ULS,s} = \frac{R}{S} = \frac{\varphi (W - F_u - S_{arch})}{F_H} \quad (3.11)$$

The reliability function describing the overturning failure modes provides a measure of the structural safety of the caisson against the risk of rotation about the base edge *OB*. It represents the balance between the stabilizing moments R , mainly arising from the self-weight of the caisson, and the destabilizing ones, each calculated as the product of the acting force and its respective lever arm:

$$Z_{ULS,o} = \frac{R}{S} = \frac{W X_g}{F_u X_u + F_H Y_H + S_{arch} X_{arch}}$$

or better

(3.12)

$$Z_{ULS,o} = \frac{R}{S} = \frac{W X_g}{M_u + M_H + M_{arch}}$$

where:

$$F_u = \frac{1}{2} p_u B \quad (3.13)$$

$$M_u = \frac{2}{3} B F_u \quad (3.14)$$

$$F_H = \frac{1}{2} (p_1 + p_3) h' + \frac{1}{2} (p_1 + p_4) h_c^* \quad (3.15)$$

$$M_H = \frac{1}{6} (2p_1 + p_3) h'^2 + \frac{1}{2} h' h_c^* + \frac{1}{6} (p_1 + 2p_4) h_c^{*2}$$

$$S_{arch} = \rho g V_{immersed}$$

$$M_{arch} = S_{arch} * X_{arch} = S_{arch} * \frac{B + A}{2} \quad (3.16)$$

X_g is the coordinate of the barycenter G , also called the center of mass, which is the point of a body or a system of bodies where the entire mass can be considered to be concentrated for the purposes of analyzing translational motion or equilibrium.

As already stated, the pressure diagrams and the corresponding forces are calculated based on the formulas proposed by Goda (2000), whose main relationships are reported below, using the wave design variables H_{max} , T_{max} and L_w , where L_w is a function of water depth h and the period T_{max} through the dispersion relation.

$$\eta^* = 0.75(1 + \cos \beta) H_{max} \quad (3.17)$$

$$p_1 = \frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos \beta) (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 \cos^2 \beta) \rho g H_{max} \quad (3.18)$$

$$p_3 = \alpha_3 p_1 \quad (3.19)$$

$$p_4 = \begin{cases} p_1 \left(1 - \frac{R_c}{\eta^*}\right) & : \eta^* > R_c \\ 0 & : \eta^* \leq R_c \end{cases} \quad (3.20)$$

$$p_u = \frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos \beta) \alpha_1 \alpha_3 \rho g H_{max} \quad (3.21)$$

$$h_c^* = \min(\eta^*, R_c) \quad (3.22)$$

$$\alpha_1 = 0.6 + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{4\pi h / L_w}{\sinh(4\pi h / L_w)} \right]^2 \quad (3.23)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \min \left\{ \frac{h_b - d}{3h_b} \left(\frac{H_{max}}{d} \right)^2, \frac{2d}{H_{max}} \right\} \quad (3.24)$$

$$\alpha_3 = 1 - \frac{h'}{h} \left[1 - \frac{1}{\cosh(2\pi h / L_w)} \right] \quad (3.25)$$

Note that h_b represents the water depth at a distance $5 H_s$ seaward of the breakwater in the offshore side. It can be calculated from the seabed slope θ , which corresponds to the tangent of the seabed angle (in degrees), as:

$$h_b = h + (5H_s \theta) \quad (3.26)$$

while β is the wave attack angle at the toe of the structure, as shown in Figure 3.17.

Figure 3.17 Definition of the angle of wave attack β .

In the present work, the variables describing the vertical breakwater geometry and materials are treated as deterministic, while the force generated by waves and sea level is modeled using a fully probabilistic approach, as described in section 2.2.2. It should be noted that the caisson weight was calculated considering that it is filled with granular material (density equal to 20,000 N/m³). Future research will focus on the probabilistic characterization of the resistance variables.

As regards the SLS, the reliability function is derived from the formula suggested by EurOtop (2018) to predict the mean overtopping discharge at vertical structures. EurOtop (2018) distinguishes between two main categories: cases with foreshore influence and cases without foreshore influence. Indeed, an influencing foreshore can significantly modify the waves by altering their shape and height through shoaling, steepening, and breaking, thus affecting the overtopping phenomenon. A practical definition of an influencing foreshore is water of shallow or intermediate depth (i.e., not deep water) at the structure toe. However, the effect also depends on whether the foreshore is horizontal or genuinely sloping, with slopes of 1:50 or steeper. In the present case, the absence of foreshore influence was verified at each realization of the performed MC simulations by applying the following relationship (EurOtop, 2018):

$$\frac{h}{H_s} > 4 \quad (3.27)$$

The reliability function for the assessment of wave overtopping failure at vertical walls in the case of no influencing foreshore is:

$$Z_{SLS} = qlim - \sqrt{gH_s^3} \cdot a \cdot \exp \left[- \left(b \cdot \frac{R_c}{H_s \gamma_\beta} \right)^{1.3} \right] \quad (3.28)$$

where a and b are empirical coefficients, and γ_β is a parameter that depend on the wave attack angle at the toe of the structure according to the following relationship:

$$\gamma_\beta = \begin{cases} 1 - 0.0033|\beta| & : 0^\circ \leq \beta \leq 80^\circ \\ 0.736 & : \beta > 80^\circ \end{cases} \quad (3.29)$$

Also in this case probabilistic characterization of the wave parameters of equation (3.28) is performed according to the methodology described in subsection 2.2.2. In particular:

$$R_c = h_{wall} - (h + h_{SS}) \quad (3.30)$$

The parameter h_{wall} , which is the height of the wave wall measured with respect to the toe of the structure, is normally distributed, and its distribution is truncated to exclude unrealistic values, through the lower (l) and upper (u) truncation limits calculated as a function of the parameter k (see equations (3.2) and (3.3)). As discussed in subsection 2.2.2, the water depth h at the toe of the breakwater follows a Normal distribution too, whose standard deviation is a function of the astronomical tide variations. The same applies to the empirical coefficients a and b , whose mean values and standard deviations are provided by EurOtop. The parameters of the above-mentioned normal distributions are reported in Table 3.VIII. The mean value of the water depth at the toe of the structure, which is different at each cross-section (C and D), is reported for the present climate as well as for the future SSP5–8.5 scenario for the years 2070 and 2100. The standard deviation of h is calculated according to Equation (2.6), considering that for the site of Vado figure h_{at} is equal to 0.194 m. The mean value of h_{wall} varies and the corresponding standard deviation is set as suggested by Lara et al. (2019). The acceptance limit q_{lim} is considered as a deterministic variable and is set equal to 0.02 m³/s m (EurOtop, 2018) for both cross-sections. Such limits correspond to significant damage or even sinking of larger yachts, noting that in the two sections under study ship mooring is not planned, and only cargo loading and unloading operations are considered. Following the state of the art, and in particular the Spanish ROM guidelines, the design lifetime of the harbor breakwater is assumed to be 50 years, while the maximum acceptable failure probability ($P_{f,Lmax}$) is set equal to 10⁻¹ for both the ULSs and the SLS. For each of the three considered climate scenarios, a MC simulation with $N_r = 2.25 \times 10^4$ realizations (i.e., life cycles of the structure) is performed in order to evaluate the probability of reaching either one of the ULSs or the SLS.

Table 3.VIII Values of the mean (m) and the standard deviation (σ) of the normally distributed variables, and of the parameter k employed to calculate the lower (l) and upper (u) limits of the truncated distributions (f = empirical coefficient of the ULS reliability function, a and b = coefficients of the SLS reliability function, h = mean water depth, h_{wall} = height of the wave wall measured with respect to the toe of the structure).

Variable	Description	m	σ	k	l	u
a [-]	EurOtop (2018) formula	0.047	0.007	-	-	-
b [-]	EurOtop (2018) formula	2.35	0.230	-	-	-
Cross-section C						
h [m]	Present climate	46.00	0.097	-	-	-
	SSP5-8.5 future scenario 2070	46.40	0.097	-	-	-
	SSP5-8.5 future scenario 2100	46.75	0.097	-	-	-
h_{wall} [m]	Dependent on the toe depth of the section	53.00	0.030	4.00	52.88	53.12
Cross-section D						
h [m]	Present climate	46.50	0.097	-	-	-
	SSP5-8.5 future scenario 2070	46.90	0.097	-	-	-
	SSP5-8.5 future scenario 2100	47.25	0.097	-	-	-
h_{wall} [m]	Dependent on the toe depth of the section	53.50	0.030	4.00	53.38	53.62

Results and discussion

Characterization of wave climate and generation of random sea storms

The extreme value analysis of the significant wave height is performed at the point shown in Figure 3.18. Figure 3.18 shows also the percentage of events classified by significant wave height and direction of origin. Following the methodology described in subsection 2.2.2, the Peak Over Threshold (POT) method is applied to identify independent storm events coming from $123.75^{\circ}\text{N}\div 191.25^{\circ}\text{N}$, which is the relevant angular sector for the analysis of wave action acting on the considered structure. According to Boccotti (2004), a threshold of 1.5 m should be adopted to evaluate independent storm events in the directions of the most energetic waves. This is done for the waves coming from $123.75^{\circ}\text{N}\div 146.25^{\circ}\text{N}$ (hereinafter sector 1) and $168.75^{\circ}\text{N}\div 191.25^{\circ}\text{N}$ (hereinafter sector 3). For the events originating from $146.25^{\circ}\text{N}\div 168.75^{\circ}\text{N}$ (hereinafter sector 2), which are characterized by lower significant wave heights, a lower threshold of 1.0 m is applied. A total of 104, 111, and 376 extreme events are obtained for sector 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The MLM method is employed to estimate the scale, shape and location parameters of the Weibull distribution of extreme significant wave height for each of the three directional sectors, which are reported in Table 3.IX. The goodness of fit is assessed at the 5% significance level using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. As an example, the cumulative non-exceedance probability calculated for sector 1 is shown in Figure 3.19. It should be noted that for the implementation of the MC simulations, the wave attack angle is defined as the bisector of each considered angular sector, which is reported in Table 3.IX.

Figure 3.18 Wave rose showing the percentage of events classified by significant wave height and direction of origin evaluated at the point representative of the offshore wave climate at Vado Ligure harbor breakwater.

Table 3.IX Average number of extreme events per year (λ) and values of the scale (α), shape (κ), and location (ζ) parameters of the Weibull distribution adapted to the extreme values of the significant wave height H_{s0} for each directional sector considered for the site of Vado Ligure.

Sector	Mean Direction [$^{\circ}\text{N}$]	λ [events/year]	α [m]	κ [-]	ζ [m]
1	135	2.74	0.46	0.98	1.50
2	157.5	2.92	0.47	0.90	1.00
3	180	9.89	0.43	0.99	1.50

Figure 3.19 Comparison between the observed extreme wave events coming from sector 1 at the Vado Ligure site and the adapted Weibull Cumulative Density Function (CDF).

To quantify the variability of the extreme wave climate among sectors, the significant wave heights corresponding to different return periods were estimated using the Weibull distribution with the parameters reported in Table 3.IX. Figure 3.20 shows that, as the return period increases, the discrepancies between the H_{S0} values estimated for the three most energetic sectors decrease. The sector with the highest offshore significant wave heights is Sector 3. Since the rounded λ is equal to 3 events/year for sectors 1 and 2, according to the methodology described in subsection 2.2, and in particular in Figure 2.2a, 150 random values of H_{S0} are generated for each of the 2.25×10^4 MC realizations, resulting in a total of 3.38×10^6 sea storms. For sector 3, where the rounded λ is equal to 10 events/year, 500 random values of H_{S0} are generated for each of the 2.25×10^4 MC realizations, resulting in a total of 11.25×10^6 sea storms. For instance, Figure 3.21a shows the random values of H_{S0} generated for the direction wave sector 1, together with the central fit curves and the corresponding 95% confidence bounds of the Weibull distribution.

In order to evaluate the peak (T_p) and mean (T_m) wave period, the sea storm duration (d_s), and the storm surge height (h_{SS}) corresponding to each randomly generated value of H_{S0} , the site-specific coefficients of the empirical relationships described by equations (2.7) - (2.10) are calibrated for the four wave data points, using the least square methods. Table 3.X reports their estimate and 95% *CBs*. Following the procedure described in subsection 2.2, and in particular in Figure 3.5b, for each random value of H_{S0} the corresponding values of T_m , d_s , and h_{SS} are generated for each directional sector. Sea storms generated for each directional sector are propagated toward the structure's toe using equation (3.7), and H_{max} is then calculated using equation (3.9), considering the current mean sea level as well as the two future projections.

Figure 3.20 Comparison between extreme values of significant wave height obtained from the Weibull distribution adapted to the extreme wave events for each sector

Figure 3.21 Generation of random sea storms for the wave data point in sector 1: (a) random values of extreme significant wave height (H_{s0}) and central fit and 95% confidence bounds (CBs) of the corresponding Weibull distribution; (b) random values of peak wave period (T_p) and central fit and 95% CBs of the corresponding site-specific relationship with H_{s0} ; (c) random values of sea storm duration (d_s) and central fit and 95% CBs of the corresponding site-specific relationship with H_{s0} ; (d) random values of storm surge height (h_{ss}) and central fit and 95% CBs of the corresponding site-specific relationship with H_{s0} .

Table 3.X Estimate and 95% confidence bounds (CBs) of the site-specific coefficients of the relationships between the significant wave height (H_{s0}) and the peak wave period (T_p), the sea storm duration (d_s), and the storm surge height (h_{ss}) calibrated for each angular sector of wave origin.

Sector of wave origin	Coefficient	Estimate	Lower 95% CB	Upper 95% CB
1	b_{T_p} [-]	10.51	10.22	10.79
	b_{d_s} [h/m]	8.06	6.95	9.20
	b_{ss} [-]	0.05	0.04	0.05
2	b_{T_p} [-]	11.87	11.42	12.33
	b_{d_s} [h/m]	19.7	17.41	22.00
	b_{ss} [-]	0.06	0.05	0.07
3	b_{T_p} [-]	12.26	12.08	12.44
	b_{d_s} [h/m]	8.30	7.65	8.94
	b_{ss} [-]	0.07	0.06	0.07

Stability performances under the present climate

The failure probability associated with the sliding or overturning of the caisson is calculated for the cross-section types C and D of the Vado Ligure vertical breakwater by applying the methodology described in subsection 2.2.1, using the reliability functions defined by equations (3.11) and (3.12), respectively, and the previously generated random present marine climate.

Figure 3.22 presents the cumulative failure probability P_f for the ULS associated with the sliding of the caisson as a function of time over the 50-year reference service life, while Figure 3.23 shows the same outcomes for the ULS associate with the overturning of the caisson. Throughout the entire reference period, the failure probability associated with sliding and overturning remains far below the acceptance limit of 0.10, demonstrating that the vertical breakwater satisfies the required stability criteria under the current marine climate. The wave action coming from sector 2 and is the most severe. The failure probabilities reached at the end of the service life corresponding to the two considered ULSs are reported in Table 3.XI, together with the performance indexes r and s calculated as described in section 2.3, for the cross-section types C and D and the three wave direction sectors. For the caisson type C, the failure probability associated with sliding or overturning is lower than for the caisson type D. Accordingly, the failure index r and the rate of growth of the failure probability s are lower for the first caisson type. This indicate that the cross-section type C is the most stable. This is due to the fact that the caisson of type C is slightly bigger, and hence heavier ($W = 1.39 \times 10^7$ N/m), than the caisson of type D ($W = 1.00 \times 10^7$ N/m), as reported in Table 3.VII. Concerning the impact of the wave motion, the results reveal that the most severe sea storms, which cause the highest $P_{f,L}$ and hence the lower r , come from the direction sector 2, followed by the directional sector 1.

Figure 3.22 Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater over the 50-years reference service life associated to the sliding of the caisson (ULS) under the present climate conditions: (a) cross-sections type C; (b) cross-section type D. The admissible threshold $P_{f,Lmax}=0.10$ is out of the limits of the plots.

Figure 3.23 Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater over the 50-years reference service life associated to the overturning of the caisson (ULS) under the present climate conditions: (a) cross-sections type C; (b) cross-section type D. The admissible threshold $P_{f,Lmax}=0.10$ is out of the limits of the plots.

Table 3.XI Failure probability of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater at the end of the structure lifetime and performance indexes associated with the sliding and overturning of the caisson (ULS) under present climate conditions.

Cross-section	Wave origin sector	Sliding			Overturning		
		$P_{f,L}$	r	s	$P_{f,L}$	r	s
C	1	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}	0.00	0.00	0.00
	2	2.67×10^{-4}	2.67×10^{-3}	6.15×10^{-6}	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}
	3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
D	1	2.67×10^{-4}	2.67×10^{-3}	6.15×10^{-6}	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}
	2	8.00×10^{-4}	8.00×10^{-3}	1.43×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}
	3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Overtopping performances under the present climate

As in the case of the ULS associated with caisson failure due to sliding or overturning, the assessment of the failure probability due to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge is performed according to the methodology described in Section 2.2.1, using the reliability function defined in equation (3.28) and the previously generated random present marine climate. Figure 3.24 shows the temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge over the 50-year reference service life, for both considered cross-section types (i.e. C and D) and for all analyzed wave direction sectors. The 95% confidence band derived from the probabilistic simulations is also reported. The dashed horizontal line represents the admissible failure probability threshold $P_{f,Lmax} = 0.10$. The results show a progressive and almost linear increase of P_f over time, revealing that the performances of the cross-section types C and D are comparable. Moreover, the outcomes highlight that the most severe wave action in terms of produce wave overtopping at the vertical

breakwater originate from sectors 1 and 2. Table 3.XIX reports the failure probability at the end of the lifetime and the corresponding values of r and s , evaluated for the cross-section types C and D and the three considered wave direction sectors. After 50 years, the cumulative failure probability reaches values of the order of 10^{-2} . Although this value remains below the admissible threshold, it is significantly higher than the probabilities obtained for the ULSs associated with sliding and overturning of the caisson. The confidence band remains relatively narrow throughout the entire service life, indicating limited variability in the overtopping response and confirming the robustness of the probabilistic estimates. Overall, the analysis indicates that excessive mean wave overtopping discharge represents the most critical limit state for the analyzed cross-sections under the present climate conditions.

Figure 3.24 Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater over the 50-years reference service life associated to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge (SLS) under the present climate conditions, including the 95% confidence band: (a) cross-sections type C; (b) cross-section type D. The admissible threshold is $P_{f,Lmax}=0.10$.

Table 3.XII Failure probability of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater at the end of the structure lifetime and performance indexes associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge (SLS) under present climate conditions.

Cross-section	Wave origin sector	$P_{f,L}$	r	s
C	1	6.84×10^{-2}	6.84×10^{-1}	1.40×10^{-3}
	2	5.88×10^{-2}	5.88×10^{-1}	1.18×10^{-3}
	3	1.21×10^{-2}	1.21×10^{-1}	2.50×10^{-4}
D	1	6.78×10^{-2}	6.78×10^{-1}	1.36×10^{-3}
	2	5.93×10^{-2}	5.93×10^{-1}	1.19×10^{-3}
	3	1.16×10^{-2}	1.16×10^{-1}	2.32×10^{-4}

Effects of climate change on the structure performances

The SLR can influence the probability of reaching both the ULSs and SLS by affecting wave shoaling and propagation, and consequently the wave characteristics at the toe of the structure, as well as by directly influencing the failure mechanism, being included into the corresponding reliability function. Specifically, for the ULSs associated with the caisson sliding or overturning, the SLR affects the wave descriptors H_{max} and T_{max} and the extension of the caisson subjected to wave pressure. Instead, for the SLS associated with excessive mean wave overtopping, the

SLR influences the significant wave height at the toe (H_s) and the relative height of the wave wall (R_c), which decreases as SLR increases. Consequently, rising sea levels act directly on all the considered failure mechanisms.

For both cross-section types C and D, Figure 3.25 and Figure 3.40 show the comparison between the cumulative failure probability associated with the ULS due to the sliding and to the overturning of the caisson, respectively, calculated for the present climate and the two projected scenarios with SLR by 2070 and 2100, considering the three wave direction sectors. Moreover, Table 3.XIII reports the corresponding values of the failure probability and of the performances indexes calculated for the two future scenarios. The results indicate that the SLR produces only negligible changes in the overall stability performances. Indeed, the future cumulative failure probability curves remain almost unchanged compared to the present-climate case. This suggests that, for the analyzed cases, the increase in water level does not lead to significant increases in wave-induced loads, and therefore the stability assessment is largely insensitive to the projected SLR scenarios.

For both cross-section types C and D, Figure 3.27 and Figure 3.28 show the comparison between the cumulative failure probability associated with the SLS due to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge calculated for the present climate and the two projected scenarios with SLR by 2070 and 2100, considering the three wave direction sectors. Moreover,

Table 3.XIV reports the corresponding values of the failure probability and of the performance indexes calculated for the two future scenarios. A significant increase in the failure probability due to excessive mean wave overtopping is observed under both future SLR scenarios and for both reference cross-sections. It should be noted that the admissible failure probability threshold of 0.10 is exceeded under the SLR2070 and SLR2100 climate scenario, if the sectors 1 and 2 are considered. This result confirms that sectors 1 and 2, although less energetic than sector 3, require greater attention due to their angle of wave impact.

To conclude, the obtained results clearly show that the SLR significantly affects only the overtopping phenomena, while its influence on the stability processes is practically negligible.

Figure 3.25 Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater over the 50-years reference service life associated to the sliding of the caisson (ULS) under the present and future climate conditions: (a) cross-sections type C; (b) cross-section type D. The admissible threshold $P_{f,Lmax}=0.10$ is out of the limits of the plot.

Figure 3.26 Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater over the 50-years reference service life associated to the overturning of the caisson (ULS) under the present and future climate conditions: (a) cross-sections type C; (b) cross-section type D. The admissible threshold $P_{f,L,max}=0.10$ is out of the plot limits.

Table 3.XIII Failure probability of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater at the end of the structure lifetime and performance indexes associated with the sliding or the overturning of the caisson (ULSs) under future climate conditions.

Cross-section	SLR	Sector	Sliding			Overturning		
			$P_{f,L}$	r	s	$P_{f,L}$	r	s
C	SLR2070 +0.40 m	1	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}	0.00	0.00	0.00
		2	3.11×10^{-4}	3.11×10^{-3}	7.08×10^{-6}	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}
		3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	SLR2100 +0.75 m	1	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
		2	3.11×10^{-4}	3.11×10^{-3}	1.10×10^{-6}	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}
		3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
D	SLR2070 +0.40 m	1	2.67×10^{-4}	2.67×10^{-3}	6.15×10^{-6}	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}
		2	8.00×10^{-4}	8.00×10^{-3}	1.43×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}
		3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	SLR2100 +0.75 m	1	2.67×10^{-4}	2.67×10^{-3}	6.15×10^{-6}	4.44×10^{-5}	4.44×10^{-4}	1.10×10^{-6}
		2	8.00×10^{-4}	8.00×10^{-3}	1.43×10^{-5}	8.89×10^{-5}	8.89×10^{-4}	2.33×10^{-6}
		3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Figure 3.27 Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater over the 50-years reference service life associated to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge (SLS) under the present and future climate conditions, including the 95% confidence band: cross-sections type C. The admissible threshold is $P_{f,L,max}=0.10$.

Figure 3.28 Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater over the 50-years reference service life associated to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge (SLS) under the present and future climate conditions, including the 95% confidence band: cross-sections type D. The admissible threshold is $P_{f,Lmax}=0.10$.

Table 3.XIV. Failure probability of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater at the end of the structure lifetime and performance indexes associated excessive mean wave overtopping discharge (SLS) under future climate conditions.

Cross-section	SLR	Sector	$P_{f,L}$	r	s
C	SLR2070 +0.40 m	1	1.03×10^{-1}	1.03	2.11×10^{-3}
		2	8.32×10^{-2}	8.32×10^{-1}	1.69×10^{-3}
		3	2.13×10^{-2}	2.13×10^{-1}	4.41×10^{-4}
	SLR2100 +0.75 m	1	1.45×10^{-1}	1.45	2.98×10^{-3}
		2	1.12×10^{-1}	1.12	2.29×10^{-3}
		3	3.59×10^{-2}	3.59×10^{-1}	7.36×10^{-4}
D	SLR2070 +0.40 m	1	1.03×10^{-1}	1.03	2.09×10^{-3}
		2	8.27×10^{-2}	8.27×10^{-1}	1.66×10^{-3}
		3	2.06×10^{-2}	2.06×10^{-1}	4.19×10^{-4}
	SLR2100 +0.75 m	1	1.46×10^{-1}	1.46	2.99×10^{-3}
		2	1.10×10^{-1}	1.10	2.23×10^{-3}
		3	3.64×10^{-2}	3.64×10^{-1}	7.52×10^{-4}

Evaluation of the return period of failure during lifetime

The failure probability at the end of the design lifetime is converted into the corresponding return period using equation (2.14). Overall, the return period associated with the failure probability at the end of the design lifetime exceeds 1,000 years for the ULSs associated to both the sliding and the overturning of the caisson, regardless of the considered cross-section type and wave origin directional sector, under both the current and future climate conditions. This value is significantly higher than the target return period required for this type of infrastructure (i.e. 475 years).

In contrast, the failure probability at the end of the design lifetime associated to the SLS due to excessive mean wave overtopping under the current climate conditions corresponds to return periods greater than 778 years for the two studied cross-sections, which can be considered

acceptable. The projected SLR further intensifies overtopping processes, leading to a reduction in hydraulic performances. Under the SLR scenarios, the return periods relative to the most critical wave direction sector decrease to approximately 460 years and 320 years for the 2070 and 2100 projection, respectively

Evaluation of the expected annual cost at the end of the lifetime

The evaluation of the expected annual cost at the end of the lifetime is not performed for the case study of the Vado Ligure harbor breakwater, due to the impossibility to retrieve documentation on the costs of repair interventions for caissons, as well as the losses resulting from the breakwater's lack of functionality within the time limits set by the project.

3.4 The case study of the Arenella harbor breakwater

Description of the case study

The probabilistic methodology for the breakwater performance is applied to the Arenella harbor breakwater, located along the northern coast of Palermo (Italy), in the central Mediterranean Sea (as shown in Figure 3.29a). The Port of Arenella occupies a strategic position along major maritime routes connecting the Suez Canal, the Strait of Gibraltar, European ports, and North African ports. The port infrastructure has historically played a key role as a local fishing and recreational harbor. However, long-term exposure to energetic wave conditions has led to progressive deterioration of the existing rubble-mound breakwater, particularly of the armor layer composed of 30 t concrete parallelepiped armor units. This degradation has resulted in reduced hydraulic stability and increased wave overtopping, adversely affecting port operability and safety.

In response to these issues, the *Autorità di Sistema Portuale del Mare di Sicilia Occidentale* commissioned the EUMER laboratory (*EUropean Maritime Environmental Research*, University of Salento) to carry out a 3D physical model investigation in a wave basin in order to update the existing breakwater section. The experimental campaign was conducted between December 2022 and March 2023, with the aim of assessing the hydraulic stability and overtopping performance of the new rubble-mound breakwater planned as an extension of the existing outer breakwater. The upgraded structure, designed by Progetti e Opere – Envitek, introduces innovative single-layer concrete armor units patented by CLI (Concrete Layer Innovative). The project is consistent with the configuration defined in the Port Master Plan (Piano Regolatore Portuale, PRP) approved in 2018 (D.A. n. 100, 30/07/2018). Compared to the previous PRP (1974), the updated layout preserves the overall geometry and dimensions of the harbor basin, while providing improved hydraulic protection. In Figure 3.29b, the real time state of the breakwater is reported.

Figure 3.29 Case study of the Arenella harbor breakwater (Palermo, Italy): (a) location of the Port of Arenella; (b) Real time state of the port of Arenella.

Due to the significant deterioration of the existing armor layer, the Port Authority has planned restoration and upgrading works aimed at enhancing hydraulic stability and reducing wave overtopping discharge. Based on combined experimental and numerical analyses, the selected upgrading solution consists of:

1. the placement of additional armor units with a 4:3 seaward slope;
2. the construction of a toe berm to improve toe stability;
3. the raising of the wave wall crest elevation up to +9.50 m above mean sea level.

The intervention includes both the rehabilitation of the existing breakwater and its extension. The main geometric features of the project can be summarized as follows and are shown Figure 3.30:

- rehabilitation of the existing breakwater over a length of 94.85 m, including the construction of a new armor layer made of Accropode™ II units (submerged portion) and Ecopode™ units (emerged portion), upgrading of the core, and construction of a wave wall.
- extension of the breakwater for a total length of 109.7 m, subdivided into:
 - a first segment of 49.7 m oriented at 25°18'23" N, including a concrete superstructure with wave wall on the seaward side and an anti-reflective quay wall on the harbor side, terminated by a 17 × 20 m head structure;
 - a second segment of 60 m oriented at 55°17'39" N, with a seaward wave wall and no quay on the harbor side;
- construction of the roundhead, protected by Accropode™ II units below water and Ecopode™ units above water;
- new toe berm protected by Accroberm™.

The extension is founded at an average water depth of approximately -13 m with respect to mean sea level and is geometrically consistent with the existing breakwater. To account for geometric variability along the structure (approximately 110 m), two representative cross-sections were defined: one along the trunk and one at the roundhead (Figure 3.31 and Figure 3.32) and consist of:

- a core made of first-category quarry stones up to elevation +1.64 m MSL (+1.20 m at the roundhead), with a seaward slope of 4:3;
- a filter layer of second-category stones, with a thickness of 1.90 m (2.10 m at the roundhead);
- a single-layer armor composed of Accropode™ II units for the submerged part and Ecopode™ units for the emerged part, including an emerged berm 10 m wide at elevation +6.0 m MSL;
- a toe berm made of Accroberm™ I units;
- a concrete crown wall, with a width ranging from 9.80 m to 8.15 m and a maximum crest elevation of +6.10 m MSL.

The adopted single-layer armor system using Accropode™ II and Accroberm™ I units is illustrated in Figure 3.33. Special attention is devoted to the toe geometry, which is recognized as a critical component for overall breakwater stability. In the present case, the toe configuration is strongly influenced by the irregular geometry of the degraded existing armor layer. As schematically shown in Figure 3.34, for cross-section type A, characterized by uniform degradation, the newly constructed toe berm directly supports the additional Accroberm™ units.

Figure 3.30 Characteristics of the Arenella harbor breakwater: a) Plan view of the actual harbor breakwater (left) and plan view of the upgraded harbor breakwater (right); b) Project for the completion of the breakwater; c) Axonometric view of the 3D model of the designed works.

Figure 3.31 Cross-shore trunk section of the harbor breakwater.

Figure 3.32 Cross-shore roundhead section of the harbor breakwater.

Figure 3.33. Single-layer armor made of artificial concrete units: Accropode™ II type (left, for submerged section) and Ecopode™ type (right, for emerged section).

Figure 3.34. Armor layer system using Accropode™ II and Accroberm™ I units.

The offshore wave climate was characterized using reanalysis data provided by the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS, Korres et al., 2021) and generated through the Med-WAV modeling system based on the WAM 4.6.2 wave model. A 40-year period (1985–2025) is considered. The model is forced by ERA5 hourly wind fields (Escudier et al., 2020) and daily-averaged currents, and includes a nested domain with a spatial resolution of $1/24^\circ$ over the central Mediterranean. To describe wave conditions along the Arenella breakwater, time series of significant wave height (H_s), peak wave period (T_p), and mean wave direction are extracted at the closest offshore data point (i.e. point P1), whose coordinates and water depth are reported in Table 3.XVI and whose location is shown in Figure 3.35.

Storm surge contributions to sea level were derived from ERA5 reanalysis data with 10-minute temporal resolution for the period 1985–2025. Future sea-level rise (SLR) was incorporated using the mean projections from the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report. Under the worst-case scenario SSP5–8.5, mean SLR values of 0.42 m by 2070 and 0.78 m by 2100 were considered.

Table 3.XV. Coordinates and depth of the selected wave data point (coordinate system: WGS84/UTM Zone 33 N).

Wave data point	Longitude [°]	Latitude [°]	Depth [m]
P1	13.39	38.16	~80

Figure 3.35. (a) Plan view and coordinates of point P1 selected for model data extraction. (b) Bathymetric survey provided by ADSP.

Simulated failure mechanisms and climate scenarios

For the present case study, two independent failure modes were analyzed:

- Ultimate Limit State (ULS): collapse of the outer armor layer;
- Serviceability Limit State (SLS): exceedance of the allowable mean wave overtopping discharge.

The corresponding reliability functions were derived within the PROMETEO project framework. For the ULS, the van der Meer (1999) damage formulation for single-layer Accropode™ II armor units is adopted, as shown in the following equation:

$$Z_{ULS} = f - \frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} \quad (3.31)$$

where, due to the lack of site-specific calibration data, the empirical coefficient was assumed deterministic and equal to $f=2.5$ (van de Meer, 1999), corresponding to design condition for the Accropode II armor layer (with $f=2.5$ for start of damage and $f=4.1$ for armor failure). It is noted that this formulation refers to the design conditions and, unlike other formulations, does not explicitly depend on additional wave parameters.

For the SLS, the EurOtop (2018) formulation for mean wave overtopping discharge was adopted, as shown in the following equation:

$$Z_{SLS} = q_{lim} - \sqrt{gH_s^3} \cdot a \cdot \exp \left[- \left(b \cdot \frac{R_c}{H_s \gamma_f} \right)^{1.3} \right] \quad (3.32)$$

where $R_c = h_{wall} - (h + h_{SS})$.

The probabilistic characterization of wave and structural parameters follows the methodology described in section 2.2.2. Again, the variables D_{n50} , Δ , h , h_{wall} , and the empirical coefficients a and b are modeled as normally distributed random variables, truncated to exclude unrealistic values. The lower (l) and upper (u) truncation limits are calculated as a function of the parameter k , as shown in equations (3.2) and (3.3). The statistical parameters adopted in the analyses are summarized in Table 3.XVI. The mean value of the water depth at the toe of the structure is reported for the present climate as well as for the future SSP5–8.5 scenario for the years 2070 and 2100. The standard deviation of h is calculated according to Equation (2.6), considering that for the site of Arenella is equal to 0.14 m, whereas the standard deviation of h_{SS} is set as suggested by Lara et al. (2019).

The acceptance limit for overtopping discharge q_{lim} was assumed deterministic and equal to 0.001 m³/s m for both cross-sections, in accordance with EurOtop (2018) criteria for small craft and yacht safety.

The design lifetime of the breakwater was assumed equal to 15 years (Puertos del Estado, 2010), and the maximum acceptable failure probability was set equal to $P_{f,Lmax}=0.15$ for both ULS and SLS. Indeed, the upgraded structure can be classified as a specific-use structure (protective works for a tourist and fishing harbor), and the required safety level is 1 but considering high risk to human life and significant economic consequences due to the selected construction scheme. For the present case, a reference return period of 92 years is obtained. For safety

reasons, and for the purposes of the present study, a design return period of 100 years is adopted. For each climate scenario (present, SSP5–8.5 in 2070, SSP5–8.5 in 2100), Monte Carlo simulations with $N_r=1.4 \times 10^4$ realizations were performed to estimate the probability of failure over the structure lifetime.

Table 3.XVI Values of the mean (m) and the standard deviation (σ) of the normally distributed variables, and of the parameter k employed to calculate the lower (l) and upper (u) limits of the truncated distributions (f = empirical coefficient of the ULS reliability function, a and b = coefficients of the SLS reliability function, h = mean water depth, D_{n50} = mean nominal diameter, Δ = relative density, h_{wall} = height of the wave wall measured with respect to the toe of the structure).

Variable	Description	m	σ	k	l	u
f [-]	van der Meer (1999) formula - trunk	2.50	-	-	-	-
	van der Meer (1999) formula - roundhead	2.50	-	-	-	-
a [-]	EurOtop (2018) formula - upgraded breakwaters	0.09	0.0135	-	-	-
b [-]	EurOtop (2018) formula - upgraded breakwaters	1.50	0.15	-	-	-
	Present climate	13	0.07	-	-	-
h [m]	SSP5-8.5 future scenario 2070	13.42	0.07	-	-	-
	SSP5-8.5 future scenario 2100	13.78	0.07	-	-	-
D_{n50}	Accropode™ II	1.97	0.03	3.00	1.88	2.06
Δ	Buoyant concrete density	1.34	0.05	4.00	1.14	1.54
h_{wall}	Dependent on the toe depth of the cross-section	22.50	0.03	4.00	22.38	22.62

Results and discussion

Characterization of wave climate and generation of random sea storms

The extreme value analysis is performed for the significant wave height data corresponding to the point P1. Prior to the application of the extreme value analysis, the modeled wave data were validated against in situ measurements from the Capo Gallo directional wave buoy, considering the same temporal window of availability of the buoy records. The validation, not reported herein, confirmed a satisfactory agreement in terms of significant wave height statistics, thus supporting the reliability of the reanalysis dataset for the subsequent probabilistic assessment.

Following the methodology described in subsection 2.2.2, the POT method is applied using a threshold equal to 1.5 m for the identification of independent events according to the definition provided by Boccotti (2004). A filter of 2.0 m is also employed to remove the lower values of significant wave height, to improve the robustness of the estimation of the probability distribution tail. As shown by the wave roses in Figure 3.36, the extreme events originate from two predominant directional sectors: a main 90°-wide sector spanning approximately 60°N–150°N (NE–ESE), and a secondary sector extending from about 0°N to 70°N (N–ENE), highlighting a clear bimodal directional dominance of the most energetic conditions. The obtained samples of extreme events are composed by 330 elements for the wave data point P1. The average number of extreme events per year calculated for each sample is reported in Table 3.XVII. The MLM is employed to estimate the scale, shape and location parameters of the Weibull distribution at the given wave data point, which are also reported in Table 3.XVII. The goodness of fit is assessed at the 5% significance level using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test.

Considering only 1 wave data point, there is no variability of the extreme wave climate along the breakwater. Since the rounded λ is equal to 7 events/year for P1, according to methodology described in subsection 2.2, 315 random values of H_{S0} are generated for each of the 1.4×10^4 MC realizations. For instance, Figure 3.37a shows the random values of H_{S0} generated for the wave

data point P1, together with the central fitted curve and the 95% confidence bounds of the corresponding Weibull distribution.

Figure 3.36 Wave roses at point P1; a) Wave climate; b) Extreme events.

Table 3.XVII Average number of extreme events per year (λ) and values of the scale (α), shape (κ), and location (ζ) parameters of the Weibull distribution adapted to the extreme values of the significant wave height H_{s0} at points P1.

Wave data point	λ [events/year]	α [m]	κ [-]	ζ [-]
P1	7	1	1.33	0.79

In order to evaluate the mean wave period (T_m), the sea storm duration (d_s), and the storm surge height (h_{SS}) corresponding to each randomly generated value of H_{s0} , the site-specific coefficients of the empirical relationships described by equations (2.7) - (2.10) are calibrated for P1, using the least square methods. Table 3.XVIII reports their estimate and 95% CBs. Following the procedure described in subsection 2.2, and in particular in Figure 3.37, for each random value of H_{s0} the corresponding values of T_m , d_s , and h_{SS} are generated at data point P1.

Sea storm generated at P1 are propagated toward the toe of the structure, considering the present mean sea level as well as the two future projections. The presence of bathymetric contours parallel to the breakwater, together with the relatively small difference between initial and final water depths (i.e. up to 13 m), justifies the adoption of a simplified approach. This approach is based on linear wave shoaling computed following Dean and Dalrymple (1991), combined with the wave breaking criteria proposed by Kamphuis (1991) and Goda (2009). Results of incident wave height at the toe of the breakwater are reported in Figure 3.38.

Figure 3.37 Generation of random sea storms for the wave data point P1: (a) random values of extreme significant wave height (H_{s0}) and central fit and 95% confidence bounds (CBs) of the corresponding Weibull distribution; (b) random values of mean wave period (T_m) and central fit and 95% CBs of the corresponding site-specific relationship with H_{s0} ; (c) random values of sea storm duration (d_s) and central fit and 95% CBs of the corresponding site-specific relationship with H_{s0} ; (d) random values of storm surge height (h_{SS}) and central fit and 95% CBs of the corresponding site-specific relationship with H_{s0} .

Table 3.XVIII Estimate and 95% confidence bounds (CBs) of the site-specific coefficients of the relationships between the significant wave height (H_{s0}) and the mean wave period (T_m), the sea storm duration (d_s), and the storm surge height (h_{SS}) calibrated for the wave data point P1.

Wave data point	Coefficient	Estimate	Lower 95% CB	Upper 95% CB
P1	b_{T_m} [-]	10.97	10.88	11.06
	b_{d_s} [h/m]	40.01	38.47.17	41.54
	b_{SS} [-]	0.006	0.003	0.008

Figure 3.38 Incident wave height computed at the toe of the breakwater for the present climate (left) and the future climate scenario in 2100 (right).

Stability performances under the present climate

The failure probability associated with the collapse of the outer armor layer of the Accropode II breakwater at the Arenella harbor was evaluated at the most critical cross-section (roundhead) by applying the probabilistic methodology described in section 2.2.1. The reliability function, expressed by equation (3.31), was formulated with reference to the Ultimate Limit State (ULS) related to armor layer instability and implemented using the Monte Carlo-generated present marine climate at wave data point P1.

It should be noted that no sufficient experimental data were available to verify the applicability of the Van der Meer (1999) stability formulation for the specific geometrical configuration of the analyzed breakwater cross-section. Therefore, the adopted stability relationship is assumed to adequately represent the structural response without direct site-specific experimental validation. Furthermore, within the applied formulation, the hydrodynamic forcing enters the stability equation only with H_s . Other hydrodynamic parameters, such as wave period or spectral characteristics, do not explicitly affect the stability number in the same manner as in other stability formulations. Consequently, the predicted structural response is less sensitive to variations in the overall hydrodynamic conditions compared to rubble mound breakwaters armored with natural rocks or other units whose stability equations explicitly include additional wave parameters (as for example the case study of Catania harbor). This characteristic contributes to a comparatively lower variability in the computed failure probability.

The stochastic characterization of offshore significant wave height, mean wave period, peak period, storm duration, storm surge, and water depth was performed as described in the previous sections. Since only one wave data point (P1) was considered and no significant distinction between the trunk and the roundhead was introduced in the probabilistic simulations, spatial variability along the structure was not addressed. Consequently, the results refer exclusively to the most critical cross-section of the breakwater, namely the roundhead section.

Figure 3.39 presents the cumulative failure probability P_f as a function of time over the 15-year reference service life, together with the associated 95% confidence band derived from the Monte Carlo simulations. The results show a gradual and nearly linear increase in failure probability. After 15 years, the cumulative value reaches approximately 10^{-2} , remaining $P_{f,L}$ significantly lower than the admissible threshold $P_{f,Lmax}=0.15$ adopted for design purposes. The narrow confidence band confirms the robustness of the probabilistic estimation and indicates limited dispersion in the simulated structural response under present climate conditions. Throughout the entire reference period, the failure probability remains well below the acceptance limit, demonstrating that the outer armor layer of the Accropode II breakwater satisfies the required stability criteria under the current marine climate. The rate of increase of the failure probability appears approximately constant over time, consistent with the assumption of stationary present climate conditions. This behavior indicates a progressive but controlled accumulation of structural risk, without abrupt accelerations during the analyzed lifetime. This analysis confirms that the outer armor layer does not approach critical conditions within the design service life. Therefore, under present climate conditions, no extraordinary

reinforcement or immediate maintenance interventions are required for the analyzed cross-section. More generally, the temporal evolution of failure probability provides useful guidance for maintenance planning. By comparing the growth of $P_{f,L}$ with a target admissible value $P_{f,L}$, it is possible to estimate the time horizon at which repair or strengthening measures may become necessary. In the present case study, however, the projected failure probability at the end of the design life remains far below the allowable threshold. The integration of probabilistic predictions with future field monitoring data would further enhance the reliability-based assessment, enabling adaptive and optimized maintenance strategies throughout the service life of the structure.

Figure 3.39 Stability performance of the outer armor layer at the roundhead of the Arenella harbor Accropode II breakwater under present climate conditions. Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f over the 15-year reference service life, including the 95% confidence band obtained from Monte Carlo simulations and the admissible threshold $P_{f,L,max}=0.15$.

Overtopping performances under the present climate

Following the same probabilistic framework adopted for the ULS related to the collapse of the outer armor layer, the failure probability associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge was evaluated at the roundhead of the Arenella harbor breakwater. The analysis was carried out according to the methodology described in section 2.2.1, using the reliability function defined in equation (3.32) and the previously generated random present marine climate at wave data point P1.

Prior to applying the EurOtop (2018) prediction formulae, the overtopping experimental data measured at the EUMER laboratory were plotted against the corresponding confidence bands to verify their consistency with the adopted formulation, as shown in Figure 3.40. The roughness coefficient and the obliquity factor were set equal to $\gamma_f=0.44$ and $\gamma_\beta=1$, in accordance with EurOtop (2018) recommendations for Accropode II armor units under 3D perpendicular wave attack conditions. The comparison shows that the available experimental data fall within the expected confidence range of the EurOtop equation, indicating that no recalibration of the overtopping formula is required for the analyzed cross-section.

Figure 3.40 EUMER 3D overtopping measurements compared with the EurOtop (2018) prediction equation for Accropode II armor units.

The probabilistic analysis accounts for the variability of offshore wave conditions and for the prescribed maximum acceptable mean overtopping discharge $q_{lim} = 0.001 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, adopted for the considered breakwater segment. The coefficient of variation of the computed failure probability at the end of the reference service life is relatively small (i.e. 0.02), confirming the numerical stability and robustness of the Monte Carlo simulations.

Figure 3.41 presents the temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge over the 15-year reference service life, including the 95% confidence band derived from the probabilistic simulations. The dashed horizontal line represents the admissible failure probability threshold $P_{f,Lmax} = 0.15$. The results indicate a progressive and nearly linear increase of P_f over time, consistent with the assumption of stationary present climate conditions. At the end of the 15-year period, the cumulative failure probability reaches values on the order of 5×10^{-2} , remaining below the admissible threshold but significantly higher than those obtained for the ULS related to armor layer collapse. The confidence band remains narrow throughout the analyzed lifetime, indicating limited dispersion in the overtopping response and confirming the reliability of the probabilistic estimation.

Overall, the probabilistic analysis highlights that excessive mean wave overtopping discharge represents the governing limit state for the analyzed cross-section under present climate conditions. While structural collapse of the armor layer is not critical, upgrading interventions are required to reduce the overtopping-related failure probability below acceptable levels. The identification of the most effective upgrading solution among different alternatives can be achieved through additional reliability-based probabilistic simulations and comparison of the resulting performance indexes, following a performance-oriented design optimization approach.

Figure 3.41 Overtopping performance at the roundhead of the Arenella harbor P_f II breakwater under present climate conditions. Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability $P_{f,L}$ over the 15-year reference service life, including the 95% confidence band obtained from Monte Carlo simulations and the admissible threshold $P_{f,Lmax}=0.15$.

Effects of climate change on the structure performances

The sea level rise (SLR) can affect the failure probability in two ways: i) by influencing the wave shoaling and propagation processes, and hence the wave characteristics at the toe of the breakwater; ii) by directly influencing the failure mechanism, being included into the corresponding reliability function. In order to quantify the effects of SLR on the structure performances, the failure probability associated with the collapse of the outer armor layer and with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge has been therefore calculated at the given cross-section of the Arenella harbor breakwater also considering the effects of projected SLR by 2070 and 2100. However, only the results corresponding to the 2100 scenario are reported herein, as this represents the most critical condition. The coefficient of variation of the failure probability is equal to 0.02 for both the ULS and SLS.

For the ultimate limit state (ULS) related to the stability of the outer armor layer, the reliability function Z_{ULS} , does not explicitly include the local water depth (h). Therefore, SLR does not act directly on the failure mechanism, but only indirectly through the wave height at the structure (i.e. H_s at the toe), which may vary under different water levels. Consistent with this formulation, the results show that the projected SLR scenarios considered here +0.42 m by 2070 and +0.78 m by 2100 with ($\sigma=0.07$) produce negligible changes in the overall performance. In particular, the cumulative failure probability curves remain nearly unchanged with respect to the present-climate case, with $P_{f,L}$ around 2×10^{-2} (Figure 3.42). This behavior indicates that, at the analyzed cross-section, the change in water level does not lead to an increase of the near-structure significant wave height, and the resulting stability assessment is essentially insensitive to the considered SLR projections.

Figure 3.42 Stability performance of the outer armor layer at the roundhead of the Arenella harbor Accropode II breakwater under 2100 SLR conditions. Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f over the 15-year reference service life, including the 95% confidence band obtained from Monte Carlo simulations and the admissible threshold $P_{f,max}=0.15$.

Table 3.XIXI Estimated values of the r and s indices and their relative percentage differences across the three tested ULS scenarios.

Climate scenario	r [-]	s [year ⁻¹]	Δr [%]	Δs [%]
Present	0.126	0.0012	-	-
Future 2070	0.125	0.0012	-0.8	0
Future 2100	0.123	0.0012	-2	0

Differently from the ULS stability function, the reliability function Z_{SLR} explicitly includes the water depth (in the term R_c). Therefore, SLR affects the failure probability through a double mechanism: (i) indirectly, by modifying wave shoaling and breaking processes and thus the significant wave height at the toe; and (ii) directly, since the water depth enters the overtopping formulation itself. As discussed by Stagnitti et al. (2022), the reliability function is generally more sensitive to variations in the significant wave height at the toe than to changes in mean sea level; thus, the two mechanisms may partially counterbalance each other. However, when the water depth explicitly enters the overtopping equation, the direct contribution of SLR becomes increasingly significant, particularly in deeper sections where depth-limited breaking plays a less dominant role.

The cumulative failure probability P_f associated with excessive mean wave overtopping under present climate conditions is shown in Figure 3.41 (baseline case). The curve exhibits a nearly linear growth over time, reaching values of about 0.037 at 15 years, remaining below the reference threshold (dashed line). The increase is progressive and regular, indicating a steady accumulation of overtopping-related risk under current marine conditions. Figure 3.43 (2100 SLR scenario) shows the corresponding results when projected sea-level rise is considered. In this case, the cumulative failure probability curve is systematically shifted upward with respect to the present-climate case. At 15 years, P_f reaches values close to 0.081, approaching the reference limit much more rapidly than under current conditions. The comparison between the two figures clearly highlights the impact of SLR on the serviceability performance of the structure:

- under present climate, the growth rate of P_f is moderate and the threshold is not approached within the analyzed time horizon.
- under SLR conditions, the slope of the cumulative curve is steeper, and the final probability of failure is significantly higher.

This behavior is consistent with the formulation of the reliability function Z_{SLS} , which explicitly includes the water depth. Consequently, sea-level rise affects the overtopping failure probability both indirectly, by modifying wave transformation processes and the significant wave height at the toe and directly, because the increased water depth enters the overtopping formulation itself, reducing the effective freeboard and increasing overtopping discharge.

The upward shift observed in the SLR scenario indicates that the direct effect of increased water level dominates the system response. The higher mean water level reduces the relative crest freeboard and enhances overtopping volumes, leading to a faster accumulation of failure probability over time. Compared with the ULS case (outer armor stability), where SLR produced negligible or even slightly beneficial effects, the SLS response is markedly more sensitive to projected sea-level rise. This confirms that, for the analyzed cross-section of the Arenella breakwater, future climate conditions are expected to primarily affect serviceability performance (overtopping control) rather than structural stability of the armor layer.

Figure 3.43. Overtopping performance at the roundhead of the Arenella harbor Accropode II breakwater under SLR climate conditions by 2100. Temporal evolution of the cumulative failure probability P_f over the 15-year reference service life, including the 95% confidence band obtained from Monte Carlo simulations and the admissible threshold $P_{f,max}=0.15$.

Table 3.XXII Estimated values of the r and s indices and their relative percentage differences across the three tested SLS scenarios.

Climate scenario	r [-]	s [year ⁻¹]	Δr [%]	Δs [%]
Present	0.375	0.0038	-	-
Future 2070	0.574	0.0063	53	65.8
Future 2100	0.788	0.0081	110	113.2

The combined analysis of the ULS and SLS results confirms that the failure mode associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge represents the most critical mechanism for the analyzed cross-section of the Arenella breakwater. While the stability of the outer armor layer (ULS) appears to be only marginally affected by projected sea-level rise, showing negligible variations or even a slight reduction in failure probability, the serviceability limit state (SLS) exhibits a clear and systematic increase in cumulative failure probability under SLR scenarios. In particular, the overtopping failure mechanism is characterized by a significant upward shift of P_f compared with the ULS case. This demonstrates that the structure performance in terms of protection against wave overtopping is substantially more sensitive to variations in mean sea level than the stability of the armor layer. Therefore, the results may provide practical guidance for maintenance and upgrading strategies: priority should be given to interventions aimed at mitigating wave overtopping (e.g., crest height increase or parapet enhancement), as this mechanism is expected to be the most adversely affected by future sea-level rise.

Evaluation of the return period of failure during lifetime

The failure probability at the end of the design lifetime is converted into the corresponding return period using equation (2.14). Very similar values are obtained under the 2100 sea-level rise (SLR) scenarios. Overall, the return period associated with ULS due to the failure of the armor layer, under both present and future climate conditions, is approximately 790 years, which is significantly greater than the target return period T_r associated to the maximum acceptable lifetime failure probability (i.e. 92 years).

In contrast, under present climate conditions, the return period associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge at the breakwater roundhead is approximately 260 years. The projected sea-level rise further intensifies overtopping processes, leading to a deterioration in structural performance. Under the 2100 SLR scenarios, the corresponding return periods decrease to approximately 120 years.

Evaluation of the expected annual cost at the end of the lifetime

The Arenella marina is located in the northern outskirts of the city of Palermo, on the eastern slope of Mount Pellegrino, adjacent to the urban fabric of the historic fishing village of the same name. The fishing village and the harbor were originally developed to accommodate the numerous fishing activities associated with the *Florio Tonnara*, a site of significant cultural heritage value that has generated both tangible and intangible legacies in the area. According to the current Port Regulatory Plan (PRP), the planned development of the port aims to enhance recreational boating activities through the provision of new berths and services tailored to the needs of pleasure craft, while maintaining the limited fishing activities currently present. From a maritime hydraulic perspective, the Port of Arenella is secured through a modification and moderate extension of the existing main breakwater, together with the construction of a limited new quay structure that will allow for the implementation of the necessary services for recreational boating.

The cumulative Expected Annual Cost (*EAC*) is evaluated at the roundhead cross-section of the breakwater using equation (2.15), distinguishing between the Ultimate Limit State (ULS), associated with the collapse of the outer armor layer, and the Serviceability Limit State (SLS), associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge.

With reference to the ULS, two cost components are considered:

- repair costs (expressed in € per unit length), estimated from the bill of quantities of the detailed upgrading design provided by the local Port Authority and updated according to the latest Official Regional Unit Price List (ORUPL).
- costs due to the interruption of port operations (expressed in €/day), derived from the 2026 forecast budget published by the local authorities.

For the SLS, usually only the costs associated with the interruption of port operations are considered. However, the costs associated with the SLS were not quantified in the present case study, due to the lack of available economic data specific to the Arenella marina.

It should be noted that the EAC is evaluated under present climate conditions only. The assessment of future climate scenarios would require projections of future repair costs, revenues, and broader economic drivers, which are beyond the scope of the present study. A comprehensive economic appraisal would require dedicated specialist analyses that cannot be undertaken within the framework of this work.

In this study, failure at the ULS is assumed to trigger the complete collapse of the armor layer at the analyzed cross-section. Specifically, the displacement of a limited number of units is assumed to initiate an unravelling mechanism, ultimately leading to the loss of stability of the entire armor and the underlying layer within the considered section. Accordingly, the repair quantity is not estimated through a partial-damage indicator over a finite segment width B . Instead, full reconstruction of the armor layer over the reference section is assumed. Consequently, the number of displaced armor units, N_{moved} , is directly estimated as the total number of units required to rebuild the armor layer within the adopted cross-section influence length for cost accounting purposes. Under these assumptions, the conventional formulation based on the damage number N_{od} is not applied, since the concept of a limited “damaged strip” is inconsistent with the assumed global collapse mechanism. For the reference section with $B=25$ m, the total number of armor units to be replaced is estimated at approximately 75 blocks.

Table 3.XXI reports the repair cost estimates corresponding to three alternative post-failure scenarios:

4. scenario 1 (worst case): all displaced armor blocks are considered lost and replaced with new ones;
5. scenario 2: 50% of the displaced units are replaced with new units, while the remaining 50% are recovered and repositioned.
6. scenario 3 (best case): all displaced units are recovered and repositioned.

The expected annual repair cost over the structure lifetime (EAC_{rep}), calculated at the roundhead cross-section under present climate conditions and considering the collapse of the outer armor layer, was evaluated for the three cost scenarios. For cost scenario 1, corresponding to the total loss and replacement of all displaced armor units, EAC_{rep} is equal to 28,734.75 €/25 m. For cost scenario 2, in which 50% of the displaced units are replaced and the remaining 50% are recovered and repositioned, EAC_{rep} is equal to 15,095.50 €/25 m. For cost scenario 3, corresponding to the complete recovery and repositioning of all displaced units, EAC_{rep} is equal to 3,609.00 €/25 m.

Table 3.XXI Estimate of the repair cost for the Arenella harbor breakwater in the case of collapse of the outer armor layer (ORUPL= Official Regional Unit Price List).

ID ORUPL	Brief description	Unit cost [€/m ³]	Quantity [m ³]			Total cost [€/25 m]		
			Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
17.2.1	Underwater recovery of natural rocks or artificial concrete blocks, including transport and placement.	48.17	0	35	75	-	1,685.95	3,609
17.3.1	Construction of artificial parallelepiped or prismatic concrete blocks (strength class C35/45, exposure class XS2, consistency class S3).	337.68	75	35	0	25,326	11,818.8	-
17.3.8	Random placement of parallelepiped or prismatic artificial concrete blocks.	45.45	75	35	0	3,408.75	1,590.75	-
Total cost [€/25 m]						28,734.75	15,095.5	3,609

Conversely, it was not possible to perform a quantitative assessment of the expected annual cost associated with the interruption of port operations (EAC_{eco}). Detailed economic data for the Arenella marina are not publicly available, and the port primarily serves recreational boating activities rather than commercial traffic. Therefore, its economic structure and revenue streams are not directly comparable to those of major commercial ports, for which standardized budgetary data are typically accessible. For this reason, the methodology for estimating costs due to interruption of port operations was not applied in the present case study. Nevertheless, as discussed in section 2.3, the proposed economic framework remains fully applicable in principle, provided that site-specific economic data are available. A reliable estimation of EAC_{eco} requires a dedicated, port-specific economic analysis tailored to the functional characteristics and revenue model of the harbor under consideration. Although a quantitative estimation of interruption costs was not feasible in the present case study, it may be reasonably speculated that, in ports where economic activities are more directly affected by operational downtime, the contribution of SLS-related failures to the total expected annual cost could become dominant, particularly when overtopping events occur with relatively high probability.

4. Conclusions

The design of restoration or upgrading solutions of coastal and harbor defense structures should account for uncertainties arising from the spatial non-uniformity of the system geometry and materials, as well as from the variability of climate forcing and the complexity of wave-structure interactions. This is possible only employing a probabilistic design method. In the context of the PROMETEO project, a probabilistic framework for the assessment of the performances of coastal and harbor defense solutions is proposed, starting from the work presented by Stagnitti et al. (2022).

According to the proposed methodology, for a certain limit state, a reliability function (Z) is defined as the difference or the ratio between resistance and solicitation. Z is derived from state-of-the-art or new calibrated design formulas describing the considered failure mechanism. The structure performances are assessed in terms of failure probability during lifetime ($P_{f,L}$). This is calculated by generating a sufficient number of random life cycles of the structure through the Monte Carlo simulation technique, and then counting the number of life cycles with at least one failure with respect to the total number of realizations. The failure probability is used to calculate performance indices, namely as r , which is the ratio between the calculated failure probability and the maximum acceptable failure probability over the lifetime, and s , which represents the rate at which the failure probability increases over time. Moreover, the expected annual cost at the end of the lifetime of the defense solution is computed, considering both cost of repair (EAC_{rep}) the costs of repair and losses resulting from the system's lack of functionality (EAC_{eco}). It is worth to point out that detailed economic studies are needed to obtain accurate estimation of the expected annual cost. In any case order-of-magnitude estimates can be made based on available bills of quantities for repair interventions similar to the one of interest, published financial statements of the economic activities that rely on the protection provided by the defense system, and economic estimates of damage to physical assets.

The proposed probabilistic framework is applied to three Italian case studies, namely the the Catania harbor rubble-mound breakwater, the Vado Ligure harbor vertical breakwater and the Arenella harbor rubble-mound breakwater.

For the case study of the Catania harbor breakwater, the upgraded configuration which implies the addition of extra armor blocks equal to the existing ones, the construction of a quarry stone toe berm, and the raising of the wave wall by one meter is investigated. The rubble-mound breakwater is represented by 44 cross-sections defined at 100-meter intervals. Each cross-section is characterized by its toe water depth and structural typology. Moreover, each cross-section has a different maximum acceptable mean wave overtopping discharge, depending on the specific function of each portion of the breakwater. Probability distribution of extreme significant wave height and site-specific empirical relationships between wave climate descriptors (i.e. mean wave period, sea storm duration and storm surge) are defined at four different data points located at approximately 20 m depth, placed in front of each of the four branch in which the structure is divided. MC simulations are run to calculate the failure probability during the breakwater lifetime (i.e. 50 years) associated with two independent failure modes: the ULS related to the collapse of the outer armor layer, and the SLS due to

excessive mean wave overtopping discharge. For the present climate and for two future scenarios including the SSP5-8.5 SLR projections by 2070 and 2100, 2.25×10^4 random structure life cycles are drawn, resulting in a total of 3.38×10^6 sea storms at each wave data point. The analysis of the obtained results revealed that the most critical failure mode for the studied harbor breakwater is the SLS related to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge. Moreover, the most vulnerable portions of the breakwater, in terms of stability of the outer armor layer or protection against wave overtopping, are identified by mapping the spatial distribution of r and s . The maps of the expected annual cost, calculated considering the costs for repairing the outer armor layer and the loss of revenue due to interruption of port operations, allow the conversion of the above-mentioned results in economic terms. The findings relative to the two future scenarios confirmed that, as expected, SLR will produce the increase of r and s , and hence the reduction of the structure performances, in terms of both stability of the outer armor layer and protection against wave overtopping. The most significant percentage increase of r and s due to SLR regards the SLS related to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge, with Δr and Δs by 2100 up to 175% and 182%, respectively. The stronger impact of SLR on wave overtopping than on armor layer stability is due to its effect not only on wave characteristics propagated at the toe of the structure, but also directly on the overtopping processes.

For the case study of the vertical-wall breakwater at the Port of Vado Ligure, the configuration inspired by the planned future design is analyzed. This configuration involves the seaward relocation of existing caissons, the construction of additional caissons, and the implementation of a wave wall at +7 m MSL, with the aim of expanding the calm-water basin of the port. Two representative cross-sections, namely C and D, are considered for the analysis. Each cross-section type is characterized by the local toe water depth and a distinct geometry. The probability distribution of extreme significant wave heights and the site-specific empirical relationships among the main wave climate descriptors are defined, considering three wave origin angular sectors. MC simulations are performed to estimate the probability of failure over the reference service life of the breakwater (i.e. 50 years), considering three limit states: i) ULS associated to the sliding of the caisson; ii) ULS associated to the overturning of the caisson; iii) SLS associated to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge. For the current climate and two future scenarios incorporating sea-level rise projections (SSP5-8.5) for 2070 and 2100, 2.25×10^4 random life cycles of the structure are generated for each of the three analyzed sectors of wave origin. For sectors 1 ($168.75^\circ\text{N} \div 191.25^\circ\text{N}$) and 2 ($146.25^\circ\text{N} \div 168.75^\circ\text{N}$), with an annual event frequency of approximately 3 events/year, 150 random H_{s0} values are generated for each of the 2.25×10^4 Monte Carlo realizations, resulting in a total of 3.38×10^6 sea storms. For sector 3 ($168.75^\circ\text{N} \div 191.25^\circ\text{N}$), with an annual frequency of 10 events/year, 500 random H_{s0} values are generated for each realization, resulting in a total of 11.25×10^6 sea storms. The analysis performed for the current climate condition revealed that the most critical failure mode for the studied breakwater is the SLS associated with excessive wave overtopping. Indeed, the ULS failure probability associated with caisson overturning or sliding remains respectively in the order of 10^{-5} – 10^{-4} over the entire service life, whereas the overtopping-related failure probability reaches significantly higher values, up to 6.8×10^{-2} for the most critical wave origin sector 1. In any case, the failure probability remains far below the allowable threshold of 0.10. Results for the two future scenarios confirmed that the SLR produces negligible variations in ULS performances, while it leads to a marked increase in SLS failure probability. In particular, by 2100 the cumulative overtopping-related failure probability approximately doubles for sectors 1 and

2, while it increases threefold in sector 3. Consequently, the performance indices r and s increase significantly for the SLS, indicating a progressive reduction of the structure's serviceability over time. Notably, for sectors 1 and 2 the failure probability associated with excessive mean wave overtopping discharge exceeds the maximum allowable limit of 0.10. The stronger impact of SLR on wave overtopping compared to caisson stability is due to the fact that, in corresponding the reliability formula, the SLR affects not only wave transformation processes at the toe of the structure, but also directly reduces the effective freeboard used in overtopping reliability function.

For the case study of the Arenella harbor breakwater, the upgraded configuration involving the rehabilitation of the existing structure and its extension through the construction of a new rubble-mound breakwater armored with single-layer artificial concrete units (Accropode™ II in the submerged portion and Ecopode™ in the emerged portion), the construction of a new toe berm protected by Accroberm™ units, and the realization of a reinforced crown wall with increased crest elevation is investigated. The breakwater is represented by one representative cross-sections of the roundhead. This cross-section is characterized by its local toe water depth and structural configuration. A single offshore wave data point (P1), located at approximately 80 m depth in front of the harbor, is adopted for the characterization of the extreme wave climate. The probability distribution of extreme significant wave height and the site-specific empirical relationships between wave climate descriptors (i.e., mean wave period, sea storm duration, and storm surge) are defined at this point. Monte Carlo simulations are performed to calculate the failure probability during the reference breakwater lifetime (i.e., 15 years) associated with two independent failure modes: the ULS related to the collapse of the outer armor layer, and the SLS due to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge. For the present climate and for two future scenarios including the SSP5–8.5 SLR projections by 2070 and 2100, 1.4×10^4 random structure life cycles are generated. The analysis of the obtained results revealed that the most critical failure mode for the studied harbor breakwater is the SLS related to excessive mean wave overtopping discharge. In particular, while the failure probability associated with the collapse of the outer armor layer remains of the order of 10^{-2} and well below the admissible threshold over the entire lifetime, the overtopping-related failure probability reaches significantly higher values, approaching 5×10^{-2} under present climate conditions. The results corresponding to the future climate scenarios confirmed that SLR produces a negligible variation in the ULS-related performance, whereas it leads to a marked increase of the SLS failure probability. By 2100, the cumulative failure probability associated with excessive overtopping approximately doubles with respect to the present scenario. Accordingly, the performance indices r and s increase significantly for the SLS, indicating a progressive reduction of the structure serviceability performance over time, while only marginal variations are observed for the ULS. The stronger impact of SLR on wave overtopping than on armor layer stability is due to the fact that, in the adopted reliability formulation, sea-level rise affects not only the wave transformation processes at the toe of the structure, but also directly reduces the effective freeboard entering the overtopping equation.

To conclude, the proposed probabilistic design framework appears suitable to support the design of restoration or upgrading solutions for coastal and harbor defense systems. Indeed, the performance and economic indexes allow the clear and rapid identification of the most critical failure modes as well as of the portion of the defense solution which require more urgent attention, taking into account also the rate at which the structure performances are expected

to decrease in time. Moreover, they facilitate the understanding of the possible effects of climate change on the defense solution performances, whose relevance is highly site-specific.

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